

UNIVERSITAT POMPEU FABRA

DEPARTMENT OF INFORMATION AND
COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES

MASTER IN SOUND AND MUSIC COMPUTING

Freesound drum sets using unconventional sounds

Author:

Lefteris STAMELLOS

Supervisor:

Frederic FONT CORBERA

August 31, 2016

Acknowledgements

I would like to acknowledge and thank the following people:

My supervisor, Frederic Font Corbera, whose expertise, diligence, eagerness and constant encouragement were crucial for going through with this thesis.

Other MTG people, most notably:

Xavier Serra, for being the mastermind behind MTG. Perfecto Herrera, for being always ready, willing and inspirational. Càrthac Ò Nuanàin and Dmitry Bogdanov, for the valuable input.

My colleagues, a colourful bunch of talented fools. I am more than glad to have gone through this with them.

My family, for the patience and the love.

My old teachers, for all the guidance.

My students, for making me proud.

My friends, for being true friends. Out of them, I need to acknowledge separately those that contributed actively to this thesis: Dimitris Theotokatos, Ioannis Karavasilis (JavaScript expertise), Elena Kokkinara (overall expertise).

Lastly, there are three more people who I feel are worth an exceptional mention.

Dimitris Papadimitriou: our great late teacher, the man who taught us the art of percussion and much, much more. He deserves all the credit in the world. I wish I knew better and told him so while he was still with us. His memory is cherished.

Panos Papiotis: MTGer, fellow Lamia-man, great friend. Frankly, if it wasn't for him, none of this would have happened.

Elisa: it's all about you and you make it all worth it.

Contents

1	STATE OF THE ART	5
1.1	The Drums	5
1.1.1	Membranophones	6
1.1.2	Idiophones	11
1.2	A Standard Drum Set Taxonomy	17
1.3	Low level Features	19
1.4	Content-Based Model Training and Evaluation	21
1.4.1	Single Percussive Strokes	22
1.4.2	Drum Transcription	32
1.4.3	Classification of unconventional percussive sounds	35
2	SYSTEM DESCRIPTION	37
2.1	Dataset Collection: “Conventional” set	37
2.2	Feature Extraction	42
2.3	Feature Selection	43
2.4	Classification	45
2.4.1	Logistic Regression	46
2.4.2	Support Vector Machines	46
2.4.3	k Nearest Neighbours	48
2.4.4	Naïve Bayes	49
2.4.5	Decision Trees	50
2.4.6	Ensemble Methods	51
2.4.7	Comparing all algorithms	53
2.5	Dataset Collection: “Unconventional” set	53
3	SELECTION OF THE DEFINITIVE LIST OF FEATURES	55
4	EXPERIMENT WITH HUMAN PARTICIPANTS: MOTIVATION, DESIGN AND RESULTS	77
5	PROOF OF CONCEPT	85

Abstract

The aim of this thesis is to investigate whether we can use sounds deriving from objects not originally designed for musical purposes to construct novel drum sets capable of efficiently functioning in a musical context. We tackle the subject by developing a system trained with standard drum kit sounds, built with the purpose of classifying random percussive-like sounds from unconventional objects under drum set instruments' labels. To this end, we collect two datasets, each including sounds of the two aforementioned types, both subsequently made freely accessible in Freesound. The former dataset is created in compliance with our drum set taxonomy which we hold to be among the most detailed in relevant literature. Our system, implemented in both the Weka workbench and python's scikit-learn Machine Learning library receives as an input selected sound features extracted with the use of one of Essentia's out-of-box extractors. After comparing a multitude of different algorithms, we concluded upon the use of k-Nearest Neighbor as the most suitable for the task at hand. After extensive experimentation we establish a list of nine descriptors to be used in our classifier, while achieving accuracy rates (calculated with tenfold cross-validation) close to the highest presented in relevant state-of-the-art studies (reaching over 90%). The efficiency of our model is tested through an experiment involving human participants, where a series of sequences performed by unconventional drum sets is rated on the basis of their ability to substitute conventional drum sets, their similarity with the later as well as the listeners' appreciation thereof. Finally, we produce as proof of concept a simple step sequencer producing drum patterns with sounds from our "unconventional" Freesound dataset, with the aim to include it in Freesound Labs.

Introduction

It is a long standing tradition between musicians of all trades to subject drummers to mockery, demoting them to the level of “peripheral” instrumentalist. Their perceived lack of legitimacy as “real” musicians, just like the rest of their colleagues, has continually placed them in a marginal position in the conscience of a wide part of the non-musician population as well. So, what drives this lasting idea? There are some possible explanations for that, but the one that really stands out is connected to the nature of the drummers’ instrument itself. The drums don’t produce notes and they are unique in that respect. Thus, some claim that the sounds they produce are non-musical. This statement implies a definition of a musical instrument as nothing more than a means to producing notes. We hold that such a definition is very narrow. Instead, we regard as a musical instrument any object created with the explicit purpose of being used to produce music. Any other object whose principal purpose is different does not belong in that category. By extension, any drummer can claim himself to be a musician. But does this also suggest that the sounds non-musical instruments produce are non-musical? In other words, is it not possible to produce music with them?

Such problems call for even broader and more complex definitions, related to the nature and impact of music itself. However, by restricting ourselves solely to the case of the drums, we can make the hypothesis that non-drum sounds can indeed produce a musical result similar to that coming out of a common drum set. Put in a different way, the question arises as to whether we can map non-drum sounds to instruments of a standard drum kit to successfully function in a musical context. This is precisely the question that drives this research work.

The first step towards approaching the subject is training a content-based model capable of efficiently classifying sounds deriving from standard drum set instruments. This calls for the collection of a sufficiently large data set of sounds and their subsequent labelling. The latter, in turn, requires that we have established a set of target classes covering at the very least the minimum of sounds every contemporary drummer is expected to be capable of producing. This sound collection is gathered from a multitude of sources, most predominantly from Freesound and is published under the CC0 creative commons license, freely available for use by

anyone interested. In doing so, we already achieve what we believe to be one of our main contributions, standing out principally due to the extensive and detailed form of our taxonomy. Our claim is made stronger if one takes into account the relevant literature, in which not two works use the same set of instruments when defining the drum kit, while in general producing taxonomies which we believe to be inadequate.

Figure 1: Our process schematically presented as a recycling metaphor: we begin with music, in the conventional sense (the standard drum set) move through an intermediate processing level (building of a classification system) and we conclude again in music (this time through drum sets of unconventional objects). In the middle of the process, we find the user, both the target (of our proof of concept, the drum step sequencer) and the evaluator (through an experiment involving human participants).

We proceed by extracting from our data a series of low level features employing Essentia's `streaming_extractor_freesound`. Out of those, an important percentage is discarded as irrelevant, either manually or by applying filter feature selection techniques, leaving us with a collection of attributes to be used as input in an assortment of different Machine Learning experiments. Those are ran using both the Weka workbench and python's scikit-learn library. The result is a classification system based on the k-Nearest Neighbour algorithm which using just 9 descriptors is capable of correctly classifying unseen inputs with a success rate bigger than

90%, acquired through testing with tenfold cross-validation. This efficiency of our model in classifying actual drum sounds is among the highest achieved in relevant literature. Still, it was developed with a different purpose, that is to build drum sets out of non-drum sounds adeptly functioning in a musical context. So, towards this end, we gathered a second set of sounds to be input to the classifier, comprised of single percussive-like events which derive from objects originally intended for uses outside of music. Again, this collection is made public in Freesound, which is another one among this thesis' contributions. Furthermore, we test our system's ability to accomplish its intended purpose through an experiment with human participants. The experiment was designed and implemented from scratch in the form of a web application (developed with Javascript and python's Flask web application framework). It includes a series of drum patterns with sounds drawn from our "unconventional" set, either chosen with the classifier or taken at random. The listeners are asked to rate the substitutability of the sequences as well as the appreciation thereof, allowing us to draw conclusions as to whether employing a classifier instead of picking sounds at random makes any significant difference.

Lastly, our work results in a simple step sequencer reproducing drum patterns with sounds from the collection of non-drum sounds published in Freesound, developed as a web application to be added in Freesound Labs.

Chapter 1

STATE OF THE ART

1.1 The Drums

The *drum set*, also known as the *drum kit*, is a collection of percussive instruments, most usually referred to simply as *the Drums*. Sound is produced from the Drums by means of striking, most usually with a wooden stick. Alternative objects used might include mallets whose striking end is wrapped with some soft material or a set of bristles connected to a handle, called *brushes*. The tendency to employ both the singular and the plural form to refer to the same thing suggests that the Drums are both an instrument and a group of instruments. The Drum, when used in the singular, indicates any type of membranophone percussion (see below). Nevertheless, in our context, the term Drums does not actually allude to a grouping of such instruments but to one that may include many other percussion¹. The exact formation of this collection is not fixed and, therefore, there is no unambiguous definition of the drum set. So, for our purpose, we need to define a *standard drum set* taxonomy.

Taxonomy is the term used to refer to the ways, the criteria and the schemata according to which we put musical instruments into different categories. Elsewhere, as in the technical domain of MPEG-7, the term “classification schemes” is used instead [Quackenbush and Lindsay, 2001].

One of the taxonomic distinctions of musical instruments relates to the concept of pitch, which, according to [FitzGerald and Paulus, 2006] is the “perceptual attribute which allows the ordering of sounds on a frequency-related scale extending from low to high”. Instruments that can convey a clear pitch sensation are referred to as pitched, while the ones that can not are known as unpitched. All instruments comprising the standard drum set are considered to belong to the latter category.

¹ Percussion is a word which appears sometimes as uncountable, others as countable, with “percussions” being the plural form of the latter.

Another criterion according to which we classify instruments is the means by which their sound is produced. [Von Hornbostel and Sachs, 1961] uses this to define the following four classes: the *chordophones*, the *aerophones*, the *idiophones* and the *membranophones*. Since all of the drum set components fall under the latter two categories, we will consider those in more depth.

1.1.1 Membranophones

Evidently, the membranophones' main component is the *membrane*, also known as *drumhead*, a piece of skin or synthetic material stretched across a frame. In the case of the drum set, one such frame is called *rim* or *counterhoop* and is attached to a cylindrical shell by means of *tension rods*, a series of tuning screws placed evenly around the shell's circumference. The more tightly those screws are fastened, the narrower the membrane's frequency response and the longer it will "ring" when struck [Howard, David M., Angus, 2009]. The acoustic quality of the membranophones' sound is strongly affected by the *normal modes* of their membranes, i.e. the shape of the standing waves forming when they are excited. The lowest frequency standing wave is known as the "first order mode", and the multiples of this are higher order modes. The first modes of vibration of a membrane can be seen in Figure 2.

Seeing as membranes do not move in a uniform way, we can infer that the sound projected from the instrument does not only depend on the modes of vibration but also on the location where it is hit. When the membrane is excited in a position close to a circular node (that is on the inner circles of modes (0,2), (1,2), (2,2) and (0,3) as seen on Figure 2), the corresponding modes will be suppressed. Thus, percussionists have a level of control over the timbre produced by a membranophone by choosing where to hit the drumhead. On top of that, it is possible to suppress the antinodes (lines of maximum displacement of standing waves) by placing an object on some location of the membrane, usually somewhere close to the rim. This technique is known as *muffling*. The membranophones considered in the following paragraphs are the ones most usually appearing as part of the drum kit: the *Snare Drum*, the *Bass Drum* and the *Tom-toms*.

The Snare Drum

As it happens with all its counterparts in the drum set, the Snare Drum has two membranes, one mounted on each side of its shell: the batter head, i.e. the playing surface and the snare head. These are constructed with numerous different methods and materials, each of which results in different timbral results, as demonstrated in [Lewis and Beckford, 2000]. The snare head vibrates against the snares, a set of metal wires which lend their name to both the membrane and the instrument itself.

Figure 2: The first 10 modes of a stretched drum membrane. The mode numbers are given in brackets as (number of diametric nodes, number of circular nodes). By node we refer to a point or line on a structure that does not move while the rest of the structure is vibrating). The plus and minus signs show the relative phasing of the vibration of different parts of the structure within each mode [Rossing, 2001].

The interaction of the snares with the snare head is enormously complex. The initial motion of the snares is relatively coherent. However, when at a later instance of the snare head's vibration cycle the snares return to strike the head, their motion is quickly randomized, leading directly to the noise-like timbre of the snare drum [Bilbao, 2012]. Part of the snares' action after a drum hit is depicted in 3. The amount of tension applied on the snares changes the actual effect they will have on the final sonic outcome. More importantly, we can detach them from the membrane using a lever and consequently completely negate their effect, resulting in a sound reminiscent of a tom-tom. The large difference brought about by engaging and disengaging the snares is documented by [Wheeler, 1989].

The two membranes are set to differ in tension, a tactic which results in spreading the modes they produce widely in frequency. So, the snare drum's sound is not pitch specific which makes it ideal for performing rhythmic patterns along other instruments independently of the key in which those might be playing.

Other design parameters affecting the snare drum's sound relate to the shell's dimensions and material. Standard snare drum diameters usually range from 10 to 16 inches (14 being by far the most usual) and depths from 3 to 10 inches (most commonly 4.5 to 6.5), with the general rule being the smaller the size, the higher

Figure 3: Snapshots of the response of a coupled membrane system (with snares engaged) to a short impulsive excitation, viewed from below, at times as indicated [Bilbao, 2012].

the pitch. As for the material, it can be some type of wood, metal or alloy, with each different type providing a different sound quality.

The fact that a drum's timbre can be modulated by hitting its membrane in different locations has already been discussed. Still, there are many other, less conventional ways to use the snare drum. [Tindale et al., 2004] is the first to pursue the automatic classification of sounds coming from different snare drum playing techniques (discussed in detail below, in section Content-Based Model Training and Evaluation). In the present work, we will deal with the following three, all of which are based on exploiting the rim:

- *The Rimshot*, resulting in a distinct loud and bright sound. Drummers and marching band percussionists produce it by hitting the rim with the shaft of the stick while simultaneously hitting the membrane with the tip (4, upper right image). Classical and Jazz percussionists sometimes perform it by resting one stick and hitting it on the shaft with the other one, in the manner depicted in upper left image in 4. Sound sample: <https://www.freesound.org/people/quartertone/sounds/146652/>
- *The Cross Stick*, also known as *Side Stick* in which the tip of a drumstick is placed near the centre of the head and the shaft of the stick is struck against

the rim opposite, thus creating a dry “click” sound similar to that of a set of claves (4, lower right image). The stroke is used to simulate claves in Brazilian bossa nova and also used for ballads in several contemporary music styles. Sound sample: <https://www.freesound.org/people/cooters1/sounds/245214/>

- *The rim hit*, referring simply to striking with the stick’s shaft anywhere on the rim. Sound sample: <https://www.freesound.org/people/mattlohkamp/sounds/33155/>

Figure 4: Three different snare drum playing techniques. The two images shown above depict two different ways to perform a rimshot. Lower left is a rim hit and lower right is a cross stick. Retrieved April 11, 2016, from http://www.marcdedouvan.com/en/instru.php?instru=snare_and_bass_drum)

All of the facts discussed above serve to demonstrate that the snare drum is an extremely diverse instrument, relying on the interaction of multiple components. If we also consider the various playing techniques which are widely employed by

Figure 5: Left: a drum pedal patent drawing [Smith, 1986]. Right: patent drawing for a damping pillow [Norris Jr, 2003]. The drum pillow 10 fits in the inside of the drum shell 14 such that the contact surface 16 impinges upon the drumhead 12.

contemporary drummers, we can see that it is capable of producing a very broad range of different timbres.

The point proven here is that if we are to create an adequate profile of the snare drum, there are two important issues to be dealt with. First, the creation of a sizeable collection of manifold conventional snare drum hit sounds and, second, the addition of sounds coming from a variety of different playing techniques.

The Bass Drum

The Bass Drum or *Kick Drum* is the largest member of the Drum Kit, producing the dullest sound. It is a direct descendant of the Bass Drums used by Symphonic Orchestras and Marching Bands, but much smaller in size, most commonly 20 or 22 inches in diameter. Moreover, instead of being carried on straps or being mounted on a base, it is simply left lying on the ground and hit with a beater whose movement is controlled by a foot pedal. Similarly to the snare drum, it has two heads whose tension is adjusted to differ and, thus, it produces no definite pitch. On top of that, drummers place inside the instrument's cavity some material which serves to muffle the kick, rendering the sound short and distinct. All things said, the bass drum's design is such that (as is the case with the snare drum) it is ideal for providing an ensemble with a steady beat.

The Tom-Toms

A tom-tom or simply *tom*, is a wooden-frame drum with two drum heads which follows the design configuration described in the *Membranophones* paragraph. One or more of them (sized between 6 and 16 inches in diameter, 6.5 and 12 inches in

depth) are fixed over the bass drum, and one is placed on the right of the player, standing on three metal legs (ranging between 14 and 18 inches both in diameter and depth). The latter is known as the floor tom.

One could argue that the toms are an exception to the rule stating that all standard drum instruments are unpitched, since drummers tend to match more closely the tuning of the upper and lower heads on each drum, in an effort to make them evoke a perception of pitch. Still, their partials are quite inharmonic and the resulting sound cannot definitively transmit notes, as understood in the context of western popular music (Table 1). Consequently, they are rarely used to play melodies, a fact which, although does not comply with the exact definition of unpitched instruments, results in categorizing the toms as such in literature.

<i>Mode</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>f/f₀₁</i>
0.1	147	1
1.1	318	2.16
2.1	461	3.14
0.2	526	3.58
3.1	591	4.02
1.2	684	4.65
4.1	703	4.78

Table 1: Frequencies of the first 7 modes of a 12 inches tom-tom along with their relation [Rossing, 2001].

1.1.2 Idiophones

The idiophones are instruments that produce sound by the vibration of their own body as a whole. All non-membranophone instruments in drum sets are idiophones, with the most notable example being the *cymbals*.

The types of cymbals included in the Drums are thin, axially symmetric plates made of metal or alloy. Figure [Rossing, 2001] shows the first five modes of a cymbal. We can see that, there are actually no circular modes for the lower frequencies. This is contrary to what happens in the case of membranes, the reason being that, while drumheads have their circumference fixed, cymbals used in drums are mounted at stands attached at their center. That central point is surrounded by a raised section with a semi-ovoid shape called the *bell*, *dome*, or *cup*.

Modes above those five presented actually do include at least one circular node. Nevertheless, those tend to be combinations of more than one mode, with frequencies that do not approximate closely harmonic series and therefore do not result in a strong pitch. All things considered, it is generally difficult to pin down

Figure 6: First five modes of a plate cymbal [Rossing, 2001]

for synthesis an artificial cymbal sound. In fact, it appears even more difficult if we consider that there is significant evidence that its vibrations exhibit chaotic behaviour. The steps leading up to chaos are displayed in the plots in Figure , depicting the response of a crash cymbal (see below details about the “crash” type) driven sinusoidally at the centre with a shaker. Each row, corresponds to different drive currents (0.3 A, 0.6 A and 1.4 A). In the first column we can see the cymbal’s phase (velocity versus displacement near the edge) and in the second the corresponding velocity spectra. At 0.3 A, the velocity spectrum has clear picks on the harmonics of the driving frequency, at 0.6 A subharmonics appear, at 1.4 A, chaos ensues. A more detailed summary of the non-linear behaviour displayed by the cymbals as well as an account of attempts to model it can be found in [Chaigne et al., 2004] There exists a multitude of different cymbal types employed by drummers, in our work we will only consider the three that are most consistently used: the *Crash*, the *Ride* and the *Hi-Hat*.

The Crash Cymbal

The Crash’s name is an onomatopoeic term inspired by the loud “crash” sound it produces when hit with full force. It comes in various different levels of thickness but always with a fairly thin edge. Diameter size of a crash cymbal generally varies from 8 to 24 inches, but by far the most common models are between 14 and 18 inches.

Most usually, drummers strike the Crash cymbal on the edge, with the side of the stick, producing a sound serving to accent a specific part of the measure. This part is most of the times the downbeat, with a tendency to come as a follow-up to a fill. The standard approach is to accompany it with a concurrent bass-drum hit.

[Rossing, 2001] identifies three prominent features in the sound of a cymbal: the strike sound that results from rapid wave propagation during the first millisecond, the buildup of strong peaks around 700-1000Hz in the sound spectrum during the next 10 or 20 ms, and the strong aftersound in the range of 3-5kHz that dominates

Figure 7: Phase plots and velocity spectra for a cymbal centre-driven at 320Hz: (a) harmonic generation at 0.3 A drive current, (b) subharmonics at 0.6 A, (c) chaotic behaviour at 1.4 A [Rossing, 2001]

the sound a second or so after striking and gives the cymbal its “shimmer”.

Another, less usual but prominent way of using the crash cymbal is by hitting it as described above and almost immediately “choking” it with the non-striking hand, in an effort to mute the aforementioned aftersound. The outcome is a much shorter, staccato effect (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/teleport8/sounds/28723/>). A useful comparison between the “choke” and the standard sound of a crash can be observed in Figure 8. Both spectrograms represent the first 500 ms of sounds deriving from the same crash cymbal, the rightmost being the “choked” one. We can see that up until about the 300 ms point the two spectrograms appear very similar and then the one on the right undergoes an abrupt change responding to the choke action. The latter’s last 200 ms still suggest the presence of some aftersound which nevertheless appears to have a less noisy or, in other words, more harmonic-like structure. By listening to that aftersound, we can observe that it does indeed hint to a pitch while being similar to the sound produced when the bell of the cymbal is hit. This makes sense if we consider that the drummer’s hand suppresses the vibrations of the main body of the instrument while the bell is left to vibrate.

Finally, we should mention that, as it tends to happen with all percussive

Figure 8: Spectrograms of the first 500 ms of the sounds of a crash cymbal hit and allowed to vibrate (left) and of the same cymbal being hit and “choked”.

instruments, the list of ways in which a crash cymbal can be used to produce sounds can go on and on. Following, we mention in short some additional manners of exciting the crash along with the reasons why these are left out of our analysis.

- Strike with the tip of the stick on the body of the cymbal. It is not that common a way to play during standard drum patterns and is reserved for the ride cymbal (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/CBeeching/sounds/117005/>).
- Strike with the tip or the side of the stick on the bell of the cymbal. Same as in the previous case (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/teleport8/sounds/28722/>).
- Excitation with a *roll* technique, similar to the one used for the orchestral timpani (multiple repeated fast hits either with the side of the stick or with the tip of a mallet covered with some soft material). It is not dealt with because, as seen in [Batista and Souza-filho, 2015], learning algorithms tend to confuse it with the standard cymbal hit. Also not common in drum patterns (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/davidjwoll/sounds/85486/>).
- Excitation with a cello or contra bass bow. It is left out because of lack of sufficient samples. Also not common in drum patterns (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/soundjoao/sounds/330135/>).

The Hi-Hat

The Hi-hat, sometimes spelled *Hihat*, is a combination of two crash-like cymbals and a foot pedal mechanism. The cymbals (almost always 14 inch in diameter) are mounted atop a metal stand. The pedal, placed at the bottom of said stand, when stepped on, moves a rod inside a hollow tube and causes the upper cymbal to detach from the lower. It most usually plays some ostinato pattern, keeping a steady beat, functioning as a kind of metronome. We will cover the following four playing modes:

- *Chick*. Another onomatopoeic term, referring to the sound the hi-hat cymbals make when they are brought together through the movement of the foot pedal. The drummer's hands are in no way involved. It is the sound heard in a standard 4/4 swing pattern at the weak parts of the measure (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/Robinhood76/sounds/61561/>).
- *Closed Hi-hat*. The cymbals are in full contact with each other and when hit they produce a short, noisy sound. It is the most usual playing mode employed in the majority of contemporary music styles (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/Robinhood76/sounds/61555/>).
- *Open Hi-hat*. The cymbals are separated. When the upper one is hit, its movement forces the lower to also vibrate. Consequently, the ensuing sound has a duration much bigger than that of the two previous (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/Matias.Reccius/sounds/45063/>).
- *Choke*. Similarly to the case of the crash, the open hi-hat's vibration is abruptly stopped, this time not with the hand but with the food pedal mechanism. The outcome can be described as a combination of the beginning of an open hi-hat sound with a chick sound. (sound sample: <http://www.freesound.org/people/CBeeching/sounds/116976/>).

The Ride Cymbal

This cymbal is similar to the crash cymbal, but, unlike the latter, its function is not to accent. Instead, it maintains steady rhythmic patterns, much like the hi-hat. Again, like all of the aforementioned, it is a diverse instrument that can be used in a multitude of ways. Nevertheless, in our work we will focus only on two manners of playing, on the *Bow* of the ride with the tip of the stick and on its *Bell*, with the tip and the side of the stick considered under the same category (see Figure 10)

Figure 9: Four modes of playing the hi-hat. From the upper left image, moving clockwise: chick, choke, open, closed.

Figure 10: Parts of a B8 Sabian 20 inch ride cymbal.

Other parts of the drum set

Apart from the above, any object that produces sound when beaten can potentially be part of a drum set. Some examples of percussive instruments which are frequently used in this context are the cowbell, the temple blocks, the rototoms, the timbales, the orchestral timpani, a large assortment of cymbals, etc. Nevertheless, for the sake of brevity, we will leave those out of our analysis.

1.2 A Standard Drum Set Taxonomy

All studies dealing with drum set-related classification problems are bound to provide a taxonomy upon which they define the task they consider and conduct the accompanying experiments. These might range from the simplest case of just the snare and the bass drum [Van Steelant et al., 2005] up to 45 different classes [Olivier Gillet, 2004]. Table 2 contains some examples of such taxonomies. It should be noted that studies covering percussive instruments outside of the drum set (as in [Herrera et al., 2003], for example) are not included. Similarly, papers using unconventional sound sources (see [Kapur et al., 2004]; [Hazan, 2005]; [Herrero et al., 2015]), targeting single instruments ([Tindale et al., 2004]; [Batista and Souza-filho, 2015]) or including classes with more than one instruments ([Olivier Gillet, 2004]) are left outside.

Below, we define our own taxonomy, using a tree form. It is inspired by the structured-in-levels taxonomy proposed by [Herrera et al., 2002] and it reflects the issues discussed in the immediately preceding paragraphs. This cannot by no means be considered an extensive record of all available drum set sounds. For instance, no modes of excitation alternative to wooden sticks were taken into account (as, for example, brushes and mallets). The decision was primarily driven from time constraint concerns, given that, if had chosen oppositely, we would have to look for (most probably scarce) samples deriving from all of our instrumental classes. Otherwise, including sounds from a few selected instruments would be inaccurate since it results in implications which do not coincide with real-world situations. For example, examining snare drum sounds produced from mallet hits being followed by hi-hat sounds produced by wooden stick strokes, would suggest that the drummer changed from mallets to sticks amidst playing, something really rare for modern drummers. Moreover, the case of the brushes would result in additional complications, given that it would then be required to allow for at least two playing techniques (striking and sweeping). All in all, we hold that this taxonomy serves to describe the minimum of the sounds a contemporary drummer is capable of producing and will be henceforth referred to as *the standard drum set* or the *standard drum kit*.

Publication	Target Drum Classes			Number of Classes	
[Gouyon and Herrera, 2001]	Bass Drum, Snare Drum, Hi-Hat			3	
[Herrera et al., 2002]	Super-Category	Basic-level	Sub-Category	9	
	Membranes	Kick Drum	Kick Drum		
		Snare Drum	Snare Drum		
		Tom	Low		
	Medium				
	High				
	Plates	Hi-Hat	Open		
			Closed		
Cymbal		Ride			
		Crash			
[Shahar, 2010]	Bass Drum, Snare Drum, Hi-Hat, Cymbal, Clap, Tom			6	
[Sillanpää et al., 2000]	Bass Drum, Snare Drum, Tom-toms, Open Hi-Hat, Close Hi-Hat, Ride, Crash			7	
[Van Steelant et al., 2005]	Bass Drum, Snare Drum			2	

Table 2: Some example drum set taxonomies

Figure 11: A four piece Ludwig drum set, the smallest widely used drum set up. It includes a kick drum, a snare drum, two toms, a hi-hat, a crash and a ride.

It must be noted that the tree structure is based on perceptual similarity criteria. So, the “snare drum w/ snares off” sound which corresponds to the sound produced by the snare drum when the snares are disengaged, is put under the “Tom-toms” category (see details in paragraph 1.1.1). Moreover, to produce the cross-stick and rim hit sounds, no hit is inflicted upon the snare drum’s membrane and the result bears a strong timbral dissimilarity with the actual sonic outcome of a hit on a snare drum with its snares engaged. Thus, they are treated as coming from the rim which is regarded as an idiophone instrument independent of the snare drum.

Idiophones and membranophones are presented separately to account for space shortage. All sounds denoted with yellow are considered as classes for the subsequent classification problem.

1.3 Low level Features

Extraction of low level features of sounds is a task aiming at describing said sounds in terms of physical quantities. In other words, it is a computational attempt at

Figure 12: The standard drum set

mapping sonic events on the acoustic domain. Nevertheless, the sounds we are interested in are produced to be used in a musical context. Approaching music-related tasks solely from an acoustic viewpoint and, thus, disregarding auditory and, by extension, perceptual factors is a flawed tactic, as it has been concretely demonstrated by [Wiggins, 2009]. [Lakatos, 2000] aims at drawing a connection between those two domains by detecting which low level features can be proven significant in perceptually discriminating between different classes of instruments. More specifically, [Lakatos, 2000] describes experiments engaging human participants, both musically trained and not trained, judging the similarity between a multitude of sounds. The experiments are conducted with three separate sets of sounds: harmonic, percussive and a combination of these two. Afterwards, the obtained similarity ratings are interpreted with the use of Multidimensional Scaling techniques. The goal is to define a number of dimensions along which the sounds considered cluster in a way useful for the detection of correlations between descriptors extracted with signal processing techniques and perceptual qualities. For the case of percussive stimuli, the experiments point to the participants' tendency to judge timbres according to two criteria, i.e. to two orthogonal perceptual dimensions: one correlating with the spectral center of gravity and the other correlating with transient properties of the signal (specifically, rise time). A third dimension did not appear to correlate with any easily interpretable acoustical correlate, although this does not mean that it does not exist. Given that these first two dimensions correspond to those found for the harmonic stimuli, [Lakatos, 2000] claims that at the most basic level of analysis, our perceptual representation of timbre is bidimensional. Other than that, the participants were able to interpret the percussive timbres in terms of modes of excitation as well as physical source characteristics, such as the material and shape of an instrument.

However, we should point out that, most usually, features constructed in the realm of signal processing with the intention to be used for sound characterization are defined so that they can describe properties which are perceptually meaningful. [Peeters, 2004] provides a comprehensive list of such features, along with short and intuitive explanations of functionality.

1.4 Content-Based Model Training and Evaluation

From here on, we examine the extraction and selection of sound descriptors along with the ensuing training and evaluating of classification models as a joined task.

Attributes extracted from a sound's signal form the basis for the task of automatically inferring the instrument to which said sound corresponds. The word *automatically* is key: it implies that we expect a computational system to develop an ability to figure out how to respond to a given problem on its own. Of course,

no system can perform such a task with zero information. Instead, it *learns* how to draw conclusions on some observation based on the feature values of some previously analyzed example data. The scientific field involved with such endeavours is called *Machine Learning*.

Relative problems can be categorized according to two criteria: the nature of the instances used as inputs at the learning level and the desired output. In the present thesis we are primarily interested in *supervised learning*, where a *learner* acquires knowledge by example, i.e. by the feature values of a set of inputs (the *training set*) whose corresponding outputs are known. More specifically, the training sets we examine are collections of percussive sounds each of which is known to correspond to one instrument out of a finite set of instruments. The acquired knowledge will allow for generalizations, that is, it allows for a system to infer the instrument from which an unlabelled sound is produced. We can see that the desired outcome (i.e. the name of an instrument) is a discrete value, known as *class*. This type of machine learning task is called *classification* and is performed by a *classifier*.

There exists a great (and ever-growing) number of classification algorithms, conforming to different machine learning principles, suited for a multitude of diverse tasks. There is not one method which can be chosen out of context as the most efficient and there can be many different ways to approach the same problem.

Out of all these options, Neural networks, Support Vector Machines and k-Nearest Neighbours are the methods most frequently used in subsequent studies (examples include [Shahar, 2010], [Tindale et al., 2004], [Batista and Souza-filho, 2015]). However, none of those appears to perform consistently better than the rest.

1.4.1 Single Percussive Strokes

A relatively small part of literature deals directly and exclusively with the subject of single percussive sound automatic classification. The most widely cited work on the topic is [Herrera et al., 2002]. In this paper, the authors attempt an extensive assessment of the performance achieved by different classification techniques, while employing feature selection techniques in order to determine the most relevant descriptors among a collection thereof. The classification scenario involves sounds drawn from the parts of a standard drum set, divided into three categories defining three different levels of abstraction and, by extension, three separate but interrelated tasks (see Table 3).

Moreover, [Herrera et al., 2002]., based on [Freed, 1990] and [Klatzky et al., 2000], assumed that the attack and decay segments of a percussive sound's envelope convey different information about the hit object. More specifically, they claim that the former contains information about the way the object is hit (e.g. whether it was with a bare hand or a soft mallet), while the latter about its shape and material

Super-Category	Basic-level	Sub-Category
Membranes(380)	Kick Drum(115)	Kick Drum(115)
	Snare Drum(150)	Snare Drum(150)
	Tom(115)	Low(42)
		Medium(44)
High(29)		
Plates(263)	Hi-Hat(142)	Open(70)
		Closed(72)
	Cymbal(121)	Ride(46)
		Crash(75)

Table 3: Sound dataset for [Herrera et al., 2002]

(e.g. whether it is a cymbal or a tom). Thus, most of the examined descriptors are segment-specific, being calculated solely for the attack part or the decay part. On top of those, Herrera et al. compute a series of global features: the Relative Energy Percent (REP) of 8 frequency bands and the means and variances of 13 Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCC). Following the application of three feature selection methods and based on how frequently they appear as relevant, the features presented in Table 4 are seen as the most important across each of the three levels defined in Table 3.

It is worth noting that there are certain descriptors which appear across all categories, namely the Zero Crossing Rate of the Attack, the Spectral Centroid of the Decay and its 3rd and 4th order moments, Decay Spectral Skewness and Kurtosis, respectively. On top of that, the REP of frequency bands have an important role in discriminating between different percussion instruments, mostly in the sub-category case. The fact, though, that some features describing the Attack part (especially the Zero Crossing Rate and the Temporal Centroid) seem to be really effective at instrument classification is contradicting with the paper’s preceding statement that information regarding the shape and material of hit objects is contained within the decay part.

Following the above mentioned selection, [Herrera et al., 2002] achieves classification success rates up to 99.3% for the super-category, 97.4% for the basic-level and 90.7% for the sub-category. Among the algorithms tested, K^* , an instance-based classifier, is the one most persistently returning high percentages of correct classifications. [Herrera et al., 2003] attempts a follow-up to [Herrera et al., 2002] by further exploring the automatic percussive sounds classification task. More specifically, it deals with a larger number of classes (extending to percussion instru-

Super-Category	Attack Zero Crossing Rate
	Decay Spectral Kurtosis
	Decay Spectral Centroid
	Decay Zero Crossing Rate Variance
	Decay Spectral Skewness
	REP of 300-400Hz band
	REP of 5-7kHz band
	2nd MFCC variance
4th MFCC variance	
Basic-level	Attack Zero Crossing Rate
	Attack Temporal Centroid
	Decay Spectral Centroid
	Decay Spectral Kurtosis
	Decay Spectral Skewness
	REP of all 8 frequency bands
Sub-category	Attack Zero Crossing Rate
	Log Attack-Time
	Attack Temporal Centroid
	Decay Spectral Centroid
	Decay Spectral Kurtosis
	Decay Spectral Skewness
	REP of all 8 frequency bands

Table 4: Most important features selected in [Herrera et al., 2002]

ments outside the standard drum kit) and addresses some issues additionally to that of identifying the most appropriate features and algorithms for our classification problem.

In the process, the authors introduce a series of novel descriptors, such as:

- The energy ratios of an extended version of the Bark scale critical bands along with 13 added Bark band-derived descriptors.

A scale of 26 instead of the standard 24 bands is used by splitting the two lowest in two, as a means to achieve better low frequency resolution. However, some adjacent bands have correlated values and as a consequence raw information in this feature is frequently seen as redundant. Thus, some additional relational and summarizing descriptors based on Bark bands are computed.

- The natural logarithm of a number of descriptors.

Some classification techniques assume a Gaussian distribution for the data. Yet, this requirement is not always held, leading to potentially inappropriate conclusions. Hoping to reverse this effect, the authors converted features whose distribution is peaky into another that is more Gaussian-like by applying a log transformation.

The authors also claim to have computed up to 207 descriptors over 1976 sounds deriving from 33 classes. However, the presented results provide an “original” set of features with a number equal to 89, without any specific explanation as to the reason behind this contradiction. In any case, as in the preceding work, a heavy reduction of the features’ number is pursued by means of feature selection procedures. Subsequently, quite a lot of different machine learning techniques are employed, from lazy learning ones (k-Nearest Neighbours) to neural networks, and from non-parametric ones (kernel density estimation) to parametric ones (canonical discriminant analysis). The best results were achieved by a Kernel Density Estimator, followed closely by those of a nearest-neighbour classifier (IB1 from Weka) and those of the Partial Decision Trees algorithm (PART) when enhanced with the use of a Boosting technique (83.1%, 81.5% and 82.8%, respectively, after Correlation-based Feature Selection). Decreasing the number of features does not appear to reduce significantly the achieved success rates.

Based on the results achieved up to this point, the authors choose to comment upon the following issues:

1. The spectral descriptors’ subset (excluding MFCCs’ variances) appears to be more effective than the temporal subset.

2. MFCCs (including variances) perform at rates similar to the whole spectral subset (including the MFCCs but not their variances) and both achieve the best overall performance.
3. Log-transformed Bark band energy ratios (BERs) yield 10% better results than raw BERs and 15% better results if Correlation-based Feature Selection (CFS) is used.
4. CFS filtering degrades around 2% the performance of all subsets but the MFCCs and the log-transformed BERs.
5. Adding the BER derived set does not improve the performance.

Given the newly obtained data, additional experiments are conducted with the use of an “alternative” set of descriptors, where the spectral ones are substituted by their log-transformed versions. MFCCs’ means and MFCCs’ variances are excluded from this swap. The maximum success rate after CFS filtering is given with the use of a Kernel Density Estimator over 40 descriptors and is equal to 85.7%. Note that neither at this nor at any other point is there a clear indication as to which is the exact list of selected features resulting in the provided success rates. Another fact worth noting is that the performance of most temporal and spectral features in [Herrera et al., 2003] cannot be compared to that of those used in [Herrera et al., 2002], since the latter are computed over the attack and decay segments while the former are global. An exception to this are the (in both cases global) MFCCs means and variances which, according to [Herrera et al., 2003] are amongst the most effective for the given task, a conclusion which might contradict the results provided by [Herrera et al., 2002]. Still, we can attribute all differences to the dissimilarity between the number and type of classes. This argument is enforced if we consider the confusion matrices. The fact that they do not appear to signify any noteworthy confusion between instruments belonging to the standard drum set, apart from being generally encouraging, implies that misclassification rates are skewed because of sounds deriving from instruments outside the scope of our work. Following, [Herrera et al., 2003] proceed with three more studies which also offer some useful insight. In study 2, they make use of Multidimensional Scaling in order to plot all 33 classes in a two dimensional plane. Contrary to [Lakatos, 2000] who uses similar techniques to achieve cognitive representations, the authors are concerned with an abstract “taxonomic” mapping of the data set. The result, obtained with the between-groups F-matrix index of similarity, reveals a definite separation between “plates” and membranophones and, again, no clustering of (and thus no confusion between) different parts of the standard drum set. Unfortunately, they do not provide any information about where and how the different classes shaped on this plane differ. Study 3 examines

	Training		Testing	
	Samples	Percentage	Samples	Percentage
Bass Drum	337	33.2%	224	18.9%
Snare Drum	259	25.5%	251	21.2%
Hi-Hat	195	19.2%	403	34.0%
Cymbal	116	11.4%	68	5.7%
Clap	97	9.5%	52	4.4%
Tom	12	1.2%	187	15.8%
Overall	1016	100%	1185	100%

Table 5: Sound dataset used in [Shahar, 2010]

the plausibility of a manufacturer identification model. High success rates in predicting the manufacturer of snares, kicks and toms (six candidates) and hi hats (two candidates) hint to an easy task, although some methodological drawbacks mentioned by the authors themselves allow for a level of uncertainty. Still, the mere indication that we might be able to reach such a level of detailed discrimination for drum kit instruments is encouraging. Finally, study 4 undertakes an additional evaluation of the generalization ability of the achieved results. The main conclusion drawn from this study is the need for a careful selection of the database examples in order to ensure the generalization capability of the learnt models. For instance, datasets which do not incorporate enough variability for each one of the used classes might produce over-optimistic results.

The automatic classification of samples drawn from the standard drum kit along with the comparison of classification techniques and optimal feature sets is also taken upon by [Shahar, 2010]. The data set used can be seen in Table 5.

Examining Table 5, we notice that the overall size of the data samples is bigger than the one used by [Herrera et al., 2002]. Furthermore, they include “Clap”, an instrument we do not consider in our taxonomy as part of the standard drum set. The five remaining instruments are identical to those comprising the Basic-Level category of the [Herrera et al., 2002] dataset. Nevertheless, there are no further subcategories defined. So, there is no clarification as to whether the Hi-Hat, Tom and Cymbal sounds present in the experiment include varying types and/or playing modes and, if they do, as to which they would be. On top of that, there is no consistent policy in the choice of size for each of the instrument sets. Samples used for training range from 12 to 337, those used in testing from 52 to 403. Meanwhile, training sets might be over ten times smaller than their testing counterparts (the case of Tom), about twice the size (cymbal) or anything in between. Three different types of classifiers were tested: Support Vector Machines (SVM), k-Nearest Neighbours (kNN) and Neural Network (NN), each with a

	Bass Drum	Snare Drum	Hi-Hat	Cymbal	Clap	Tom
Brightness	✓	✓				
Rolloff		✓				✓
Irregularity					✓	
Roughness				✓		
Decay			✓	✓		
Pitch		✓	✓			
MFCC1	✓	✓				
MFCC2					✓	
MFCC5		✓				
MFCC7				✓		
MFCC11		✓	✓			
MFCC13				✓		

Table 6: Optimal features for each of the instrument classes in [Shahar, 2010]

multitude of different parameters. The feature vectors are extracted with the use of MIRtoolbox and are consequently subject to selection. The technique used is Forward Feature Selection in which features are sequentially added to an empty candidate set until the addition of further features does not increase performance over 0.5. During the training stage, there are 6 SVM linear kernel classifiers trained, one for each class, using a one-versus-all approach. As a result of this procedure, features presented in Table 6 were considered optimal for each of the instrument classes.

The better performance of specific descriptors for certain classes has an apparent direct link to the classes' unique characteristics: the hi-hat is very short and high-pitched, therefore, decay and pitch stand out, and the cymbals' sound is long, bright and noisy. Such intuitive connections cannot be made for the rest of the results, though. Table 7 includes the accuracy percentages achieved by all three classifiers (the number of neighbours which resulted in the numbers seen is not specified).

Some useful conclusions can be drawn from the data presented in Table 7. The first issue that comes to our attention is the great deal of fluctuation in the success rates achieved for the same instrument class from different algorithms, especially in regards to the classes below Snare Drum in Table 7. The SVM algorithm has the advantage of producing a different decision machine for each class. Thus, it can isolate the class unique characteristics, even when a small training set is introduced. Classifiers that do not have this advantage, on the other hand, perform badly in cases where the training set is small.

Method	kNN	SVM	KK
Bass Drum	82%	88%	81%
Snare Drum	80%	85%	93%
Hi-Hat	58%	72%	74%
Cymbal	74%	47%	19%
Claps	87%	79%	4%
Tom	1%	84%	0%
Overall	60%	79%	61%

Table 7: Accuracy rates in [Shahar, 2010]

All things considered, it is clear that some algorithms are better at detecting certain classes than others. In fact, for every class there is an algorithm that performs very well. Consequently, the argument can be made that applying all algorithms and taking a joint decision might yield better performance.

[Batista and Souza-filho, 2015] describes a series of experiments conducted with the objective of researching different algorithm and feature options for a classification task focused on one sole percussion instrument family, that of the cymbals. More specifically, they attempt a two-level classification of sounds, covering:

1. the type of the cymbal
2. the playing mode/technique.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the only study which focuses on the above two groups of classes. In total, 1052 Paiste cymbal sounds were used. Table 8 provides a full description of the data set. Each of the cymbal types contains instruments varying in material, texture, curvature, thickness and diameter.

Moreover, 110 descriptors are considered, separated in 5 groups: Linear Spectral Frequencies (LSF), Linear Frequency Cepstrum (LFC), MFCC, Temporal and Spectral. During experiments, there is no care taken for the distinct effect each unique descriptor might have when in separation from the rest of its group. Instead, training and evaluating considers only those 5 collections as inseparable units, assuming that a more careful selection is insignificant. We hold that this approach is misguided, since it disregards the specific functionality of different features.

Out of a set of different classifiers tested, those that consistently performed better are Random Forest (RF) and Support Vector Machine (RBF Kernel, $C = 3.0$ $\gamma = 0.01$). For the task of classifying both the type and playing method, highest accuracy rates are given for SVM with the LSF feature set (86.49%) and for RF with the Temporal set (86.02%). As for the task involving only the type of the instrument, rates are predictably higher (96.59% for SVM with LSF, 89.95% for

Sounds - level 1	Sounds - level 2	#level 2	#level 1 (%)
China	Edge	51	99 (9.41)
	Roll	48	
Crash	Edge	152	303 (28.80)
	Roll	151	
Hi-Hat	Chick	75	227 (21.58)
	Closed	77	
	Open	75	
Ride	Bell	107	344 (32.70)
	Body	113	
	Edge	124	
Splash	Choke	36	79 (7.51)
	Edge	43	

Table 8: Sound dataset used in [Batista and Souza-filho, 2015]. For level 2 sounds see paragraphs 1.1.2, 1.1.2, 1.1.2.

RF with Temporal). The confusion matrices reveal that confusion occurs almost exclusively between crash and ride cymbals.

Consequently, the authors repeated the experiment employing both the LSF and the Temporal sets at the same time. The resulting descriptor set results in improved rates in the type plus playing technique classification task, with the best performance obtained by the SVM (91.54%).

In summary, [Batista and Souza-filho, 2015] provides proof that the seemingly demanding task of discriminating between percussion sounds down to such a specific level as that of the cymbal type and manner of beating can be tackled at a very satisfactory level.

Similarly, [Tindale et al., 2004] deal with an even more specific task: the automatic classification of different playing modes on the snare drum, a research subject which, to our knowledge, no other study has targeted. Seven modes are considered: one is a playing technique (rim shot), one relates to the object used to strike the drum (brush stroke) and the other five depend on the location of the hit on the membrane (centre, near-centre, halfway, near-edge, edge).

Over 20 features are reported to have been tested, but, similarly to [Batista and Souza-filho, 2015], the results provided only mention collections of descriptors. Nonetheless, we are presented with the four different window sizes used by those descriptors: 512, 1024 and 2048 samples long as well as equal to the Attack section. The latter is defined as the length of the signal from the onset of the sound to the point of maximum amplitude. Table 9 demonstrates highest success rates achieved for all seven modes, using three different classification algorithms, either with

Figure 13: Locations of hits on the snare drum membrane and representations of snare drum sounds ([Tindale et al., 2004]).

Best of All		All Features		Temporal Features	
		%	window	%	window
Algorithm	Neural Networks	89.3	Attack	79.9	512
	kNN	94.9	Attack	92.0	2048
	SVM	86.6	Attack	68.8	2048

Table 9: Best success rates of [Tindale et al., 2004] when all classes are examined.

Best of All		All Features		Temporal Features	
		%	window	%	window
Algorithm	Neural Networks	99.8	Attack	99.3	2048
	kNN	99.4	1024	99.1	1024
	SVM	99.6	2048	98.1	2048

Table 10: Best success rates of [Tindale et al., 2004] when the Rimshot, Brush and Edge classes are examined.

the total of the extracted features or for a subset containing only those labelled as “Temporal”.

kNN exhibits the best performance for both descriptor sets. Results under the “All Features” category are predictably higher and decidedly direct us towards a window of length equal to the Attack section. Still, seeing as kNN’s rates have similar values, the decision between the two feature sets would have to depend on the size and nature of the samples collection. On top of the above, [Tindale et al., 2004] tests some additional sets of classes. Here we present the Rimshot, Brush and Edge classes (RBE), given that it attempts a discrimination between two of the classes we are also interested in. In Table 10 we can see the accuracy results for the RBE class.

Considering the nature of the data set these accuracy levels are indeed impressive. Those achieved solely with the Temporal Features even more so, since they only include the following descriptors: Temporal Centroid, Attack Time, global RMS, Zero Crossing Rate and the RMS of four frequency bands: 0-200Hz, 200-1000Hz, 1000-3000Hz, 3000-20000Hz.

1.4.2 Drum Transcription

Most research studying the classification of single percussive sounds defines the task as part of a broader pipeline. In general, it is presented in the context of drum

Instrument Alone or Prominent	
Snare Drum, Rimshot or Clap	1440
Bass Drum	1652
Hi-Hat or Cymbal (alone)	1558
Conga, Tom, Djembe, Tabla	462

Combinations	
Bass Drum + (Snare Drum, Rimshot or Clap)	53
Snare Drum + (Tom or Congas)	44
Bass Drum + Snare Drum (Tom or Congas)	12
Bass Drum + (Tom or Congas)	106

Table 11: Sound database for [Olivier Gillet, 2004].

loop transcription, in which case the classification follows the segmentation of the drum loop into single sonic events. This approach to drum transcription is labelled by [FitzGerald and Paulus, 2006] as *segment and classify*. Other methods mentioned in literature (namely *separate and detect* and *match and adapt*) are not related to our project. Nevertheless, those single event segments do not always coincide with instrumental classes the way they are defined in the studies described above. The reason is that they might include sounds coming simultaneously from more than one different instrument.

[Olivier Gillet, 2004] studies the automatic transcription of drum loops, aiming at assisting content-based methods for querying drum loops from drum loops databases. With the use of 315 manually annotated drum loops containing 5327 sounds (strokes on both single and multiple instruments simultaneously), the authors define two taxonomies corresponding to the drum sounds from the extracted segments, a detailed and a simplified one. The former accounts for all the appearing instrumental combinations while the latter gathers some instruments in a reduced number of categories 11.

The features extracted from the audio signals include: The mean of 13 Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients including coefficient zero, calculated on 20 ms frames with an overlap of 50% and averaged over the stroke duration, 4 spectral shape parameters defined from the first four order moments, and 6 Band-wise frequency contents parameters corresponding to the log-energy in six pre-defined bands (in Hertz: [10-70] Hz, [70-130] Hz, [130-300] Hz, [300-800] Hz, [800-1500] Hz, [1500-5000] Hz). Classification is done with Support Vector Machines and Hidden Markov Models, which are useful in that they account for the context within which each stroke takes place. The simplified taxonomy results in significantly better success rates, with SVM reaching up to 83.9% accuracy.

SVM was the classification algorithm of choice for [Van Steelant et al., 2005]

	LSVM		GSVM	
	BD	SD	BD	SD
C	0.5	8	0.25	8
γ	-	-	0.256	0.064
accuracy	94.98	97.63	95.58	97.63
F1	93.30	96.34	94.12	96.34
#SV	391	179	965	350

Table 12: Results for [Van Steelant et al., 2005].

as well as undertaking the recognition of Bass and Drum sounds when in isolation or overlapping with other drum sounds. [Van Steelant et al., 2005] does not use pre existing recordings of drum sequences and thus does not include a segmentation stage. Instead, the following procedure is followed: first off, the 656 snare drum and 604 bass drum sounds from real samples are gathered. Then, the authors select 16 measures from each one of 32 songs in standard MIDI format and generated 8 variations for each track by selecting at random pairs of bass and snare drum from the set of samples while the other drum sounds were drawn from a standard MIDI drum set. The audio generated by playing back the MIDI files using these sets of drum sounds was recorded, yielding 256 audio files in total. The isolated drum sounds were added to the data set. The onset time of each event and whether it is a positive or negative instance for the binary classifiers was determined by the timing and labelling information available in the MIDI files. The information in the MIDI files thus represents the “ground truth” for the corresponding recorded audio renderings. The samples considered do not have a fixed length. For that reason, the computation of the descriptors over a frame of fixed size at the beginning of each sound was deemed preferable. The size of said frame is chosen equal to 100ms after evaluating the performance of Linear SVM with several different window sizes. The results obtained with the use of SVM of linear and Gaussian kernel are presented in Table 12.

As we see, accuracy percentages are rather high but, then again, the study only considers the cases of the Snare and the Bass drum, a task which is seen as rather simple. After all, [Gouyon et al., 2000] proves that one dimension is sufficient for discriminating between the Snare and the Bass drum, even when they are considered within the context of polyphonic music, where percussive sounds need to be detected from segments extracted from music tracks. This dimension is defined as the Zero Crossing Rate descriptor. Other studies whose object is the classification of sounds within drum loops include [Gouyon and Herrera, 2001] and [Sillanpää et al., 2000].

1.4.3 Classification of unconventional percussive sounds

Some relevant research is engaged in the description and classification of sounds which do not derive from standard percussive instruments but are meant to imitate those with the product of some alternative sound source. An example is that of BeatBoxing, a vocal percussive performance technique which has been continuously developing in a non academic context for over 30 years now (for more details on the characteristics of the BeatBoxing vocal style we refer to [Stowell and Plumbley, 2010]). It has been studied for the purposes of either generating voice controlled expressive drum rhythms, or retrieving drum loops through spoken queries. The latter is the subject of [Kapur et al., 2004]. The authors collected 75 sound-files by two different “beatboxers”, divided in three categories: 25 vocal bass drums (a vocal hit that is characterized by lower frequency coming from the chest of the performer), 25 vocal snare drums (a vocal hit that is created by the quick pass of air through the teeth) and 25 vocal high hats (a vocal hit characterized by a “S” sibilance sound, created by the tongue arching upward to the roof of the mouth). Backpropagation Artificial Neural Networks are employed for the classification of those three sound types on the basis of one feature only, with Zero Crossing Rate, Spectral Centroid, Spectral Roll-Off, Linear Predictive Coefficients and MFCC being tested. All descriptors resulted in a rather high number of successful classifications, with Zero Crossing Rate achieving again the highest percentages, reaching up to a 97.3% accuracy rate. A slightly extended taxonomy is used by [Hazan, 2005] which discriminates between two cases for the Hi-Hat, considering the closed and the open ones separately. A classification accuracy of 90% is obtained with the C4.5 algorithm improved by means of Bootstrap Aggregating. The accuracy rate is obtained in a test involving 2 performers whose recordings were not used in the training set and give an idea of the accuracy that can be reached in a real world application with encouraging results. Other studies concerned with the classification of vocal drumming include [Stowell and Plumbley, 2010].

[Herrero et al., 2015] describes a different case of unconventional percussive sounds’ classification, being as it studies the possibility of mapping sounds generated using everyday desktop objects (i.e., pencils, boxes, sticks, etc) into drum sounds. The produced application manages to classify with high accuracy levels percussive sounds from said objects with the use of a Linear Discriminant Analysis classifier taking as input a feature vector including Zero Crossing Rate, Spectral Rolloff, Spectral Flux and the third MFC coefficient.

Chapter 2

SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

2.1 Dataset Collection: “Conventional” set

The first problem one has to face when dealing with a classification task is the collection of a data set. In our case, we had to search for online sources of drum sounds corresponding to the classes defined in our Standard Drum Set Taxonomy (see drum set taxonomy subsection). Naturally, not all sounds are suitable for the task at hand simply by virtue of being attributed to the labels of our taxonomy. The requirements to which our sounds conform along with the sources from which they were drawn are described in the following paragraph.

First off, we required our dataset to be “publishable”, so the sounds should not be constraint to any licensing restrictions. In other words, we took care so that each one is available under the public domain waiver or any one of the following: BY, BY-SA, BY-NC [Cre,]

This means that we could not take advantage of drum sound data sets developed/published for commercial purposes and, thus, our available sources were significantly reduced. Therefore, we relied on a good level of web data extraction from several different web sources. The most prominent one, as expected, was [Fre,]. Other than that, sounds were obtained from the following:

- <https://ccrma.stanford.edu/workshops/dsp2008/sound-library/>
- <http://bespin.org/richie086/sp/>
- <https://www.reddit.com/r/Drumkits/>
- <https://rytmenpinne.wordpress.com/sounds-and-such/salamander-drumkit/>

- <http://www.emstechlab.com/library/sound/SoundPak/Percussion%20Instruments/>
- <http://tylergrund.com/mp3/>
- <http://99sounds.org/drum-samples/>
- <http://www.audiopropellor.com/room-boom-free-drum-kit/>
- <http://www.analogedrums.com/products/big-mono/>
- <http://www.musicradar.com/news/drums/sampleradar-1000-free-drum-samples-229460>
- <http://rekkerd.org/nsa-custom-series-drumkit-free-acoustic-dr>
- <http://www.paiste.com/e/cymbalfam.php>
- <http://www.samgreene.com/sams-sonor-samples>
- <https://theproaudiofiles.com/weiss-drums-the-maio-colletion/>
- <https://www.orangetreesamples.com/blog/free-jazz-funk-drum-sample-library>
- <http://www.mpc-tutor.com/mpc2000-sounds-samples/>
- http://wiki.laptop.org/go/Sound_samples
- <https://soundcloud.com/one-minutemusic>

The quality of each single sound was assessed solely on the basis of our perceptual criteria, i.e. listened to and subsequently evaluated as suitable for our purposes or not. So, with an aim to ensure that our resulting classifier will be reliable and useful, we cared for our training data to be:

- diverse, so that classes are complete with as many different cases falling under the same instrument category, while remaining
- consistent, that is in conformity with class characteristics, as defined in subsection 1.2. Other than that, we assured a minimum
- recording quality, meaning that sounds with excess unwanted artefacts were not taken into account. Moreover, we decided that our sounds should be

- as “natural” sounding as possible, without added effects. The logic behind this decision is that, too many effects would distort sounds and their features in a manner that would skew the classification results uncontrollably.

Accumulating a set accordant with our requirements proved to be rather time consuming. Quality expectations and time restrictions resulted in some classes not being as large as we would want them to be. Although resources for “ubiquitous” instruments such as the snare or kick drums came in abundance, with relevant Freesound samples reaching the thousands (see, for example, <http://www.freesound.org/search/?q=bass+drum>), we had trouble acquiring large enough sets for more “obscure” cases. For instance, we only managed to gather under the “crash choke” and “rim hit” classes 38 and 58 sounds, respectively. Nevertheless, deciding on the appropriate class size for a classification task is dependent upon the problem at hand and, based on the state of the art, one could hold that these numbers are not that small after all. Still, there is more to be taken into consideration: all classes provided to the learner would have to be equal in size. When given unbalanced inputs, classification models might not function as expected ([Galar et al., 2012],[He and Garcia, 2009]).

This is not always the case, yet, we decided that it would be safer to ensure equally sized classes, something which would naturally result in them being as large as the smallest, i.e. containing 38 instances each. It has already been debated in 1.1.1 that, in order to achieve a satisfactory representation of the snare drum, we need to gather a sizeable set of diverse sounds. 38 would simply not suffice. As a compromise, we settled for “pruning” our taxonomy tree, as seen in subsection 1.2, moving one level up. Put differently, we accounted only for instruments comprising the standard drum set, with playing techniques and playing modes put under the category defined by the instrument upon which they are applied. For example, our “rim hit” and “cross stick” classes had to be added up into a single “rim” class. Thus, we ended up with the following seven classes: Snare, Kick, HiHat, Tom, Rim, Ride, Crash. The smallest of those (Rim) numbers 228 instances. Consequently, the six remaining were sampled in a manner such that would ensure that all subclasses would be represented (each single sound taken at random) while keeping a bias towards the most usually appearing subclasses. The results can be seen in 13.

Finally, before heading on to the feature extraction task, we discarded those parts from each sound that corresponded to silence. The issue with silent intervals is that they result in most descriptors to change their behaviour rapidly when encountered with them. For example, the spectral centroid attribute would inflate, its values ascending rapidly towards infinitum. After all, silence does not contain any relevant information in our context. Thus, using the SoX command line utility [sox,] we removed all silent parts longer than 0.1 seconds.

Class	Subclass	Subclass number of sounds	Class number of sounds
Snare	Snare On	200	249
	Rimshot	49	
Kick	Kick	250	250
Hi-Hat	Hi-Hat Closed	100	235
	Hi-Hat Open	45	
	Hi-Hat Choke	45	
	Hi-Hat Chick	45	
Crash	Crash Edge	212	250
	Crash Choke	38	
Ride	Ride Bow	125	250
	Ride Bell	125	
Rim	Rim Hit	58	228
	Cross Stick	170	
Tom	Tom Low	70	250
	Tom Medium	70	
	Tom High	70	
	Snare Off	40	

Table 13: Our drum sound data set, used for training the learner.

Figure 14: Our standard drum set taxonomy. In colour, the “instrument level”, corresponding to our target classes.

2.2 Feature Extraction

Having brought our training set to its finalized form, we subsequently proceeded with the feature extraction task. To this end, Essentia's `streaming_extractor_freesound [ext, a]` command-line feature extractor was employed. This program is the implementation of `streaming_extractor_music [ext, b]` used by Freesound's API for sound analysis. It is primarily aimed for batch computations on large music collections, providing a wide selection of spectral, time-domain, rhythm and tonal descriptors as well as metadata. Freesound's API documentation [fre,] includes an extensive description of all available descriptors. Before the analysis takes place, `streaming_extractor_freesound` mixes down all the audio files' channels to mono. Moreover, it applies an equal-loudness filter to the signals for the computation of the following features: `spectral_centroid`, `spectral_kurtosis`, `spectral_spread`, `spectral_skewness`, `dissonance`, `spectral_entropy`, `spectral_contrast_coeffs`, and `spectral_contrast_valleys`. The audio analysis parameters' default values (which were kept as such) are the following: the sample rate is equal to 44100Hz and the frame/hop sizes for frame-based features are equal to 2048/1024 samples when belonging in the lowlevel category and 4096/2048 when in the tonal one. Additionally, as far as attributes computed over time are concerned, on top of their frame-by-frame output values, we are given access to a number of their distributions' statistical representations. Instead of using the former, we chose to keep two of the latter: `mean`(the arithmetic mean) and `var`(the variance). Furthermore, when providing our learner with a training set, we want that each one of its instances' features corresponds to no more than one single value. Therefore, the mean and the variance of one descriptor are considered as two separate descriptors. Likewise, attributes which are computed band-wise, such as Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients (MFCCs), Spectral Contrast, Gammatone Frequency Cepstral Coefficients, etc. are split according to frequency band. Thus, for example, the mean of the 1st MFC Coefficient is regarded as a different descriptor than the mean of the 3rd MFC Coefficient. This does not only make sense computationally but logically as well: calculating the differences between a sound's whole range of MFCCs with that of another is like contrasting their whole spectra. There is too much information included in the comparison and too little we can take back from it in the form of solid, intuitively meaningful conclusions.

2.3 Feature Selection

After completing the aforementioned feature extraction procedure, we are left with over 300 unique descriptors for each one of our sound collection's instances. Introducing all of those attributes to our learner without any intermediate processing steps is not optimal for a number of different reasons. First of all, one needs to assess whether the information contained within each individual feature is actually useful for the task at hand. In our case, we can intuitively conclude right from the beginning that some of the extracted attributes are not useful. For example, since our stated aim is to build content-based models, attributes placed under the Metadata label (i.e. tags, keywords, etc) have no place in our analysis. Moreover, the sounds we are interested in are single sonic events and, thus, describing them using rhythm-related terms does not make any sense. Therefore, Rhythm descriptors (beats per minute, position of beats, loudness of beats, etc) cannot be taken into account. Furthermore, it has already been argued in Chapter 1.1 that the standard drum set's sounds are considered to be non-pitched. They have no such qualities as music key, they do not form chords and, in the great majority of cases, they cannot be attributed to any single chroma bin. Consequently, Tonal attributes such as the tuning frequency, key scale, chord scale, etc are of no use. It follows that all features extracted by the `streaming_extractor_freesound` placed under the aforementioned categories need be discarded as irrelevant.

Apart from evaluating features on the basis of their individual quality, we need to additionally do so according to their relation to other present features. More specifically, it may be the case that two or more descriptors are highly correlated. Keeping more than one of them results in including duplicate information in our analysis. Naturally, such attributes are seen as redundant and retaining them is pointless.

One could argue at this point that, disposing of features due to their redundancy or irrelevancy might only serve to aggravate our work, since their presence does not directly affect the performance of other, more useful descriptors. Yet, the pursuit of a reduced feature space is driven by the need to resolve some really detrimental issues. Whenever a new attribute is introduced, our feature space grows with an order of magnitude equal to the number of the input data points, that is, it expands exponentially. Other than the obviously adverse effect this has on execution time, it results in data becoming increasingly sparse in the space it occupies. Many learning algorithms cannot perform efficiently under such circumstances and in order to overcome this phenomenon, usually referred to as the *Curse of Dimensionality*[Friedman, 1997], we need to decrease the number of used features.

Another undesirable phenomenon which can be regulated by adequately controlling the relation between the number of data points and their attributes is

Overfitting[Hawkins, 2004]. With this term we refer to the case where a learning model uses excessive information to describe a dataset, up to the point where it adapts to noise data. Consequently, such a model becomes too case-specific and loses its generalization ability, that is, the ability to produce reliable predictions when given new, previously unseen data. Naturally, the opposite phenomenon, colloquially referred to as *Underfitting*, is also possible: exceedingly decreasing the number of extracted descriptors will result to a learner incapable of correct predictions due to restricted knowledge of the data. Overfitted and underfitted models are formally said to present high *Variance* and high *Bias*, respectively.

Finally, downsizing our feature space clearly aids in improving model interpretability. Producing a system whose underlying process is incomprehensible, where the resulting predictions cannot be intuitively linked to the used attributes, prevents us from understanding its strengths and limitations and consequently from building better models. It is worth noting at this point that, although feature selection results in a space of reduced dimensionality, it is not considered a *Dimensionality Reduction* procedure. This term is actually reserved for a different group of techniques, such as Principal Component Analysis and Singular Value Decomposition, which aim to create new combinations of attributes and will not be considered in the present analysis.

Choosing which descriptors to retain and which to reject simply based on intuition is a basic form of feature selection. Other than that, there exists a multitude of techniques based on statistics and information theory one can employ, grouped into the following three categories ([Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003]):

Wrapper Methods test multiple different subsets on a given predictor, evaluate their performance based on the accuracy of the resulting predictions and select among them the optimal subset. In spite of having been proven rather efficient, wrapper methods were not considered for two reasons. On the one hand they are quite computationally intensive. On the other, they are algorithm-specific: different classifiers may work best with different sets of attributes and wrapper methods' purpose is to provide the ideal set for the classifier at hand. This makes feature selection an integral part of the procedure while our purpose was to use it as a supplementary tool, helping us reduce the load of choosing from a large collection which descriptors to not account for.

Embedded Methods are those that are used during the learning process by certain algorithms, either being by definition part of their "workflow", or included by choice as a form of enhancement, e.g. through the addition of weights on some features. The former will be the case for two of the algorithms we will consider, namely Decision Trees and Random Forests.

Filter Methods measure the intrinsic value of each unique feature using statistical tests, independently of the algorithm they are intended to be used in. Maybe the simplest approach is based upon the application of a variance threshold to the

values of each separate feature for all dataset instances. Any feature that does not meet this threshold is subsequently removed. The logic behind this decision is that, if the values of one feature do not vary enough for different data points, it follows that this particular feature does not serve to distinctively portray different classes. Indeed, after implementing this simple measure we cut down the number of descriptors to 132.

Other than the Variance Threshold technique, there exist numerous different Filter Methods for feature selection. We chose to assess each individual descriptor's usefulness based on the Information Gain Ratio metric. As its name would imply, Information Gain evaluates the amount of information with respect to the classification target we gain by introducing this particular attribute, measured in Shannon's information entropy. Unfortunately, this metric as is may introduce unwanted bias in certain cases. For instance, when a descriptor acts as a unique identifier of some result, its Information Gain is maximum while not necessarily contributing to the generalization ability of the classifier. This effect is coped with by introducing the attribute's intrinsic value in the denominator, resulting in the Information Gain Ratio. Consequently, we obtain a ranking of all our features from most to least informative. Although the chosen metric does not account for the relationship between different descriptors (as, for example, would do the Correlation Based Feature Selection), it is an adequate tool for assorting a big collection of attributes for subsequent experiments.

2.4 Classification

In the immediately following paragraphs, we explore the problem of selecting the right algorithm for efficiently tackling the classification of our "conventional drum sounds" dataset of 7 classes. There exists a great number of such algorithms with new ones being constantly introduced [Domingos, 2012]. Naturally, different types of problems call for different solutions and selecting the most suitable one among those available can be based upon a multitude of criteria. Some classifiers tend to be more easily interpretable than others (e.g. Decision Trees when compared to Neural Networks), to require shorter training times (k-Nearest Neighbours related to a Support Vector Machine with a polynomial kernels) or to be faster at producing predictions (for example, decision trees enhanced with the AdaBoost technique generally have faster prediction speeds than Random Forests). Likewise, a Naïve Bayes classifier should probably be preferred over k-Nearest Neighbours if provided a noisy data set while the reverse decision would be more likely in case one would prefer to avoid feature selection. Nevertheless, all of the above are examples of generalizations which do not always apply and should not be taken at "face value". Instead, the safest method would be to simply experiment with

Logistic Regression

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	94.44 (1.57)	93.15 (1.86)

Table 14: Results obtained with the Logistic Regression algorithm.

different methods and decide upon the best performing.

Towards this end, we consider a series of different available algorithms and run experiments in two ways: using the full set of features as well the 50 highest ranking among them, according to the rankings provided by the application of the Information Gain Ratio criterion. The motivation behind testing two sets was assessing whether a reduced set results in significantly smaller success rates or not. Subsequently, we extract the resulting classification accuracy rates, calculated by means of tenfold cross-validation and, based upon the comparison of said rates, we select which algorithm we will use to build our model. In the process, we also attempt a short description of each algorithm.

2.4.1 Logistic Regression

Logistic Regression, in spite of what its name may allude to, is not a regression technique but rather a classification one. In fact, the term Regression serves to show that the technique is based on fitting a linear model to the feature space. The term Logistic, on the other hand, is used in reference to said linear model, which is a Logistic Function.

The functionality of logistic regression is that it maps a point x in d -dimensional feature space to a value in the range 0 to 1. This value represents the probability of the instance to belong to a specific class. By applying a threshold to this probability, we can then predict the class to which instance should be assigned. Thus, this threshold represents the decision boundary in the feature space.

2.4.2 Support Vector Machines

A SVM is a large margin classifier: it functions by defining the hyperplane which separates the different classes (*decision boundary*) by the maximum geometric distance, based on the location of the points which are most difficult to classify (*support vectors*). More usually than not, the feature vectors corresponding to different classes are not linearly separable. In that case, the hyperplane is defined with the use of *Kernels*, i.e. transformations which map data into a new vector space, while preventing excessive inflation of dimensionality. For our problem, we will consider two types of Kernels: the Radial Basis Function (RBF) kernel and the Polynomial 3rd degree kernel.

Figure 15: Standard Logistic function. Image source: [Log,]

SVM with 3rd degree polynomial kernel

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	98.29 (1.02)	97.10 (1.14)

SVM with RBF kernel

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	93.64 (1.73)	82.31 (2.64)

Table 15: Results obtained with Support Vector Machine algorithm, using a 3rd degree polynomial kernel and a RBF kernel.

Figure 16: Different SVM classifiers in the iris dataset. Image source: [SVM,]

2.4.3 k Nearest Neighbours

K Nearest Neighbours is an algorithm which functions on the assumption that a data point will most probably belong to the class to which it bears the strongest “resemblance”. Intuitively, this would be the class to which other closely located points (its nearest neighbours) belong.

The first step towards applying the algorithm is defining the nearest neighbours’ vector, which depends on two parameters: a metric used to compute the distance between two points and the number of neighbours to consider, i.e. the value k . In our experiments we tested the Euclidean and Manhattan distance metrics and decided on a k equal to 1. The latter choice increases the chances of overfitting, but we opted for it nevertheless, given the other measures we took to prevent the occurrence of such a phenomenon.

After obtaining the nearest neighbour list, the class of the point is determined by a majority vote, with the option to weight the votes according to distance. The results shown below (Table 16) were obtained with the application of Weka’s version of k -NN, meaning a standard k -NN preceded with a scaling of the feature values to a range from 0 to 1.

Figure 17: The iris dataset distributed in classes using a 15-Nearest Neighbour classifier. Image source: [kNN,]

k-NN with Euclidean distance

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	97.42 (1.24)	97.87 (1.03)

k-NN with Manhattan distance

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	98.39 (0.93)	97.72 (1.02)

Table 16: Results obtained with k-Nearest Neighbour algorithm, using the Euclidean and the Manhattan distance metric.

K^* , a permutation of k-NN having been proven in [Herrera et al., 2002] to be effective in drum sound classification, was considered but eventually omitted because it was computationally expensive.

2.4.4 Naïve Bayes

Bayes classifiers provide probabilistic frameworks for solving classification problems. More specifically, the basis for those frameworks is the Bayes Theorem, which states that the probability of class C given a set of features \mathbf{x} is:

$$p(C | \mathbf{x}) = \frac{p(\mathbf{x} | C)p(C)}{p(\mathbf{x})}$$

likelihood
prior probability

posterior probability
evidence

We can see that solving the classification problem depends on finding the class C that maximizes the posterior probability $P(C|\mathbf{x})$. The denominator $p(\mathbf{x})$ (the *evidence*) will always be equal to 1 in this types of problems, while $p(C)$ (the *prior probability*) can be easily calculated by the input data. It follows that our problem is equivalent to choosing C such that $p(\mathbf{x}|C)$ (the *likelihood*) is maximum. This is a problem of great complexity, given that, in the general case, the attributes comprising the vector \mathbf{x} have a number of dependencies such as conditional dependencies, positive correlation and negative correlation. Nevertheless, in order to overcome this obstacle, we can assume that given a class C , there is independence among attributes \mathbf{x} , which would result in the likelihood to be calculated as follows:

$$p(\mathbf{x}|C) = p(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n | C_i) = p(x_1 | C_i) p(x_2 | C_i) \dots p(x_n | C_i)$$

The assumption is naive and, as such, the name of the classifier functioning under it is Naive Bayes Classifier. The result is a fast and simple algorithm which, in spite of its premise not being realistic in most cases, may be effective even when features have dependencies. It is robust to isolated noise samples and irrelevant attributes, but is not robust to redundant features. Moreover, in case that one of the conditional probabilities is zero, the whole expression of the likelihood probability becomes zero.

Naïve Bayes

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	90.20 (2.19)	89.69 (2.18)

Table 17: Results obtained with the Naïve Bayes algorithm.

2.4.5 Decision Trees

A decision tree is a structure reminiscent of a flowchart or, in a more illustrative example, an upside down tree, i.e. one that has its root on top and leafs on bottom. *Root* and *leafs* are actually terms that are also used in the context of machine learning applications. The former indicates the initial point (*node*) where

PART

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	92.14 (2.03)	92.16 (2.17)

Table 18: Results obtained with the PART algorithm.

C4.5

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	91.68 (2.16)	92.16 (2.17)

Table 19: Results obtained with the C4.5 Decision Tree algorithm.

a decision to split the data is made, based on some evaluation metric. The latter is the final node which holds the resulting class label.

For a set of observations S , the following recursive logic algorithm is applied:

- If every observation in S is the same class or if S is very small, the tree becomes an endpoint, labelled with the most frequent class (it has become a single leaf or, in other words, we have reached a final classification decision).
- If S is too large and it contains more than one class (meaning we are “standing” on a node “midway” to a leaf), find the best rule based on one feature to split it into subsets, one for each class.

The main issue to be resolved in the above method is the criterion upon which will determine how the data will be split into subsets. This is an attribute value test, such as gini impurity, variance reduction or information gain. The latter is the criterion of choice for the decision trees we are using, the C4.5 (and more specifically its Weka implementation, J48) and PART.

2.4.6 Ensemble Methods

With the term ensemble methods we refer to techniques which rely on the combination of the predictions of a number of different estimators, all built with the same learning algorithm. This approach aims at producing classifiers of improved generalization abilities and robustness compared to a single estimator.

There exist two families of ensemble techniques, the *averaging* and the *boosting* methods.

- Averaging methods construct several classifiers independently and then average their predictions. Most notable among them is the Random Forest technique, built from a collection of Decision Trees in the following manner:

PART with AdaBoost

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	96.07 (1.39)	96.30 (1.40)

Table 20: Results obtained with the PART algorithm, enhanced with the AdaBoost technique.

C4.5 with AdaBoost

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	96.29 (1.63)	96.30 (1.40)

Table 21: Results obtained with the C4.5 Decision Tree algorithm, enhanced with the AdaBoost technique.

first off, the mode of many decision trees is taken, resulting in a forest. Then, those are processed by means of “bagging”, which stands for bootstrap aggregating and basically refers to sampling with replacement (‘an element may appear multiple times in one sample). This results in slightly perturbed versions of the data (some instances will not appear in one sample, some will appear more than once and thus will have more “weight”), and, thus, the forest will now be a “bagged” forest. Lastly, some randomness is used in selecting the attribute to split on, for instance by randomly selecting an attribute or by selecting an attribute from a random subset, resulting, after all, in a Random Forest. This procedure leads to high performance because it decreases the variance of single trees, without increasing the bias. The average of many trees, in contrast to single trees, is not sensitive to noise in the training set, as long as the trees are not correlated. The trees’ de-correlation is actually what bootstrap sampling ensures by showing them different training sets.

- In boosting methods, on the other hand, work by choosing a base algorithm (again, most usually decision trees) and iteratively improving it by accounting for the incorrectly classified examples in the training set. In contrast to averaging methods, boosting ones are sequential. AdaBoost, probably the most prevalent among them, functions on the basis of the assumption that by focusing on marginal cases (that is the ones closest to the decision boundary) we are able to “boost” our accuracy rates.

Random Forest

Feature set	Full set	50 Highest Ranking
Accuracy rate (variance)	96.78 (1.29)	96.52 (1.43)

Table 22: Results obtained with the Random Forest technique.

Algorithm	SVM (Poly. full set)	k-NN (Manh.)	SVM (Poly.)	Random Forest	C4.5 (AdaB.)	PART (AdaB.)
Accuracy rate	98.29	97.72	97.10	96.52	96.30	96.27
(variance)	(1.02)	(1.02)	(1.14)*	(1.43)*	(1.40)*	(1.47)*

Table 23: Comparison of several different classifiers.

2.4.7 Comparing all algorithms

Out of the above classification techniques, the one resulting in the highest accuracy rate is Support Vector Machine with a polynomial kernel receiving as input our feature set in its entirety. Nevertheless, this is not optimal given that our aim is to keep the number of the used descriptors as low as possible. Thus, we conduct an additional experiment, comparing the above mentioned classifier with other models employing the reduced feature set, in order to test whether this can result in a classifier producing an accuracy rate which will not be significantly smaller. The results of this comparison can be seen in Table 23, the asterisk next to the accuracy rate indicating a significant difference between SVM’s results with the full feature set and those of the technique under which the asterisk appears. We observe that the only method whose rates are not significantly worse is k-Nearest Neighbour when applied with the Manhattan distance metric. Based on this observation, this is the algorithm we will be using for all of our subsequent classification experiments.

2.5 Dataset Collection: “Unconventional” set

In order to verify our stated research hypothesis, we need to map non-drum sounds to instruments of the Standard Drum Set. Towards this end, we proceeded with the collection of a set of sounds conforming to the following rules:

1. To be “percussion-like”, i.e. to have a sharp attack and be either abrupt or cymbal-like.
2. To derive from sources which do not originally and predominantly serve to be used in a musical context.

3. To be publishable, i.e. to be available under the public domain waiver or any one of the following: BY, BY-SA, BY-NC [Cre,].

With the above in mind, we ended up with a collection of 1136 sounds, from random beaten objects (cutlery, furnitures, tubes, doors, etc) as well as other abrupt sounds (barks, hisses, scratches, etc). The big majority of those was obtained through our personal recordings, which were conducted using a simple Zoom handheld recorder [Zoo,]. Other than that, the following, sounds were drawn from the following sources:

1. http://wiki.laptop.org/go/Sound_samples
2. <http://www.freesound.org/>
3. <http://www.musicradar.com/news/tech/sampleradar-533702>

All silent parts longer than 0.1 seconds were removed using the SoX command line utility [sox,].

Chapter 3

SELECTION OF THE DEFINITIVE LIST OF FEATURES

Having concluded that the k Nearest Neighbour algorithm is the best suited for the task at hand, the next step towards building our classifier was to decide upon a definite list of descriptors. There exists a series of requirements we had to consider while at this procedure. First of all, we aimed at keeping the list of features as short as possible, for the same reasons behind the application of feature selection techniques, as stated in 2.3. Secondly, some of the descriptors were included solely on the basis of their contribution in discriminating between one single instrument from the rest. Thirdly, we chose certain descriptors due to their efficiency in handling another binary classification task, that of separating two instruments which tend to frequently be the cause of “confusion”, as in “the one being misclassified as the other”. Classification efficiency is assessed using the accuracy rate, precision and recall metrics, as well as examining the confusion matrix. All of those metrics were obtained with the use of tenfold cross-validation.

Naturally, the Information Gain Ratio rankings were considered before making any of the decisions involved. The very first thing we observe is that the three highest ranking features for the general problem involving all seven classes are Zero Crossing Rate, Spectral Centroid and Spectral Rolloff [Peeters, 2004]. The Spectral Centroid attribute is informally described as the gravity centre of a spectrum and functions as a metric for that intuitive quality of a sound which we generally identify as “brightness”. Spectral Rolloff returns a frequency under which a percentage of the total energy (in our case, 85%) is contained. Zero Crossing Rate, finally, is simply the rate at which a signal changes from positive to negative or back.

Right away, we can logically deduce a correlation between these three. For example, high frequencies by definition correspond to a rapidly changing signal and by extension we expect them to have big zero crossing rate values. A sound’s excerpt with predominantly high frequency content will inevitably have the majority

of its energy accumulated in an elevated frequency area and that is where the gravity centre of the spectrum will lie. The exact opposite behaviours will be demonstrated for the case of low frequencies. It follows that all three descriptors' values have a strong linear relationship with one another, a fact which is aptly demonstrated in Figure 18.

Figure 18: The training set sounds' distribution of values of three correlated descriptors: Spectral Centroid, Spectral Rolloff and Zero Crossing Rate

We conclude that we can keep just one of those three features and discard the other two as redundant. We chose to retain Zero Crossing Rate, as it is the simplest to compute and it has been repeatedly proven in literature to contribute decisively in relevant tasks (see paragraph 1.4). Indeed, simple visual inspection of Figure 19 allows us to infer that most of the classes are distinguishable up to a satisfactory level along just this one dimension. Still, two pairs of classes appear to be exempt from this tendency: kick sounds could easily be misclassified as tom ones, as is the case for rim and ride sounds. Thus, we need to detect which attributes serve to efficiently differentiate those instruments.

We proceed by initially considering the kick and tom classes and examining the resulting feature ranking for the binary classification task involving only those two. Best ranking is tristimulus 3 [Peeters, 2004], indicating that tom has its values distributed in a small low area which would mean that its harmonics from the 4th and above have a weak presence relatively to the first three, while the kick has

Figure 19: The Zero Crossing Rate values of training set sounds along all 7 classes.

for the same descriptor values which are generally bigger and a lot more spread. Studying the other two tristimulus coefficients, we see that for the case of the tom, tristimulus 1 has relatively high values (mostly bigger than 0.5) and tristimulus 2 is relatively low (predominantly between 0 and 0.4). The values for the kick, on the other hand, have in all three cases a much rather wide distribution. We can infer that toms have a relatively strong fundamental frequency (and by extension emit some sense of pitch) while the kick's harmonic distribution is inconsistent (i.e. is noisy). This is even better illustrated by the descriptor ranking third, the pitch instantaneous confidence. This attribute measures the confidence with which the pitch of an audio expert is calculated through application of a YIN pitch detection algorithm [De Cheveigné and Kawahara, 2002], ranking between 0 and 1. The kick sounds' pitch instantaneous confidence values are generally very low, denoting that the kick is a strongly non-pitched instrument, while the tom sounds' values vary a lot, with a majority scoring over 0.5 and sometimes reaching up to 0.9, suggesting the presence of a sense of pitch. Lastly, the feature ranking second is the average of the signal's derivative after its maximum weighted by its amplitude [str,]. This coefficient helps discriminating impulsive sounds, which have a steep release phase, from non-impulsive sounds. Clearly, tom sounds are less impulsive than kick ones.

Independently of this ranking, after validating a binary classifier for the case

of those two instruments, using one of the aforementioned attributes at the time, we got the following accuracy rates: 81.8% with pitch instantaneous confidence, 79.2% with tristimulus 3 and 73.8% with derivative after maximum. Based on those results, we decided upon keeping the first one.

Figure 20: Training set sounds belonging to the Tom and the Kick classes separated along the mean pitch instantaneous confidence dimension.

In the same vein, we continue by examining the ride and rim classes in separation from the rest. The best ranking descriptor is duration [Dur,]. This makes great sense, since ride, whether hit on the bell or the bow, emits a lasting sound, while the rim, no matter the playing technique, relates to much shorter sounds. Predictably, this property results also in derivative after maximum being a very effectively discriminatory attribute (93.9% when tested alone). Nevertheless, none of those two were chosen. The reasoning was that, in spite of the silence removal in preprocessing, some presence of silence is to be expected (at least 0.1 seconds). After all, the level under which we consider a signal to be silent is not absolute. This would affect both of the aforementioned metrics and, consequently, we opted for the effective duration attribute [Peeters, 2004], which calculates the time that signal is perceptually meaningful, using a bigger threshold (in our case, 40% of the signal's maximum value). Sure enough, the binary classifier employing solely the effective duration feature has an accuracy rate of 94.76%.

With these added features, presumably we should achieve a good level of discrimination between the two pairs of instruments appearing as overlapping

Figure 21: Training set sounds belonging to the Ride and the Rim classes separated along the effective duration dimension.

in Figure 19 and, thus, along with zero crossing rate, we expect to be able to achieve a good accuracy rate solely with three attributes. Truly, we managed a 81.77% accuracy rate with Weka and 76.45% in python's scikit learn machine learning library. Moreover, we can see in Figures 22 and 23 that it is possible to visually discriminate up to a satisfactory point our classes in the space defined by those three features. Nevertheless, we can still improve our accuracy rates. We proceed likewise by considering more pairs of classes which result in mutual misclassifications, based on the confusion matrix seen in Table 24.

Confusion Matrix							
	crash	hihat	kick	ride	rim	snare	tom
crash	199	24	0	25	2	0	0
hihat	31	181	0	9	7	6	1
kick	0	2	228	0	1	0	19
ride	39	2	0	208	0	1	0
rim	2	1	0	0	172	47	6
snare	0	4	3	0	50	188	4
tom	0	0	21	0	1	4	224

Table 24: Confusion Matrix of the classifier which uses 3 features: Zero Crossing Rate, Effective Duration and Pitch Instantaneous Confidence.

Figure 22: All 7 classes' distribution in 3 dimensions: Zero Crossing Rate, Effective Duration and Pitch Instantaneous Confidence.

Examining the “crash versus hi-hat” case, we find that the highest ranking feature discriminating between these two is spectral entropy [Misra et al., 2004]. This does not seem particularly intuitive. By entropy we refer to that same measure of information, choice and uncertainty mentioned in paragraph 2.3. That same metric is used to estimate the “peakiness” of a spectrum if we convert that spectrum into a probability mass function (PMF). It has been tested predominantly for speech recognition, differentiating between voiced and unvoiced sounds [Shao et al., 2009]. Interestingly enough, the Entropy attribute appears to have an important correlation with two “noisiness versus sinusoidality” measures, spectral crest and spectral flatness (Figure 24).

Weka tackles the binary classification task at hand with an accuracy rate of 88.45%. Also, adding spectral entropy to our analysis results in the accuracy rate for the 7-class problem (now treated with the use of four features) to increase to 85.4%. We could argue that this descriptor serves to separate noisy sounds from less noisy ones. This argument is made stronger if we consider Figure 25 which shows that spectral entropy is efficient at separating all cymbals, ride being the least and hi-hat the most noisy.

Nevertheless, there remains a good level of confusion between the Crash and Ride cymbals. As it has been discussed in paragraph 1.1.2, striking the crash cymbal results in a rapid wave propagation immediately followed by buildup of

Figure 23: Pair plots for 3 dimensions: Zero Crossing Rate, Effective Duration and Pitch Instantaneous Confidence.

Figure 24: The training set sounds' distribution of values of three correlated descriptors: Spectral Entropy, Spectral Crest and Spectral Flatness.

strong peaks around 700-1000Hz which last for some milliseconds. With that in mind, one could hold that the crash cymbal will have a longer attack time (i.e. the time duration from when the sound becomes perceptually audible to when it reaches its maximum intensity) relatively to other standard drum kit instruments. Therefore, we introduce the Log Attack Time descriptor [Peeters, 2004] which computes the log (base 10) of the attack time of a signal envelope. By default, the start of the attack is estimated as the point where the signal envelope reaches 20% of its maximum value in order to account for possible noise presence. Also by default, the end of the attack is estimated as the point where the signal envelope has reached 90% of its maximum value, in order to account for the possibility that the maximum value occurs after the logAttack, as in trumpet sounds.

When examining Figure 26, it becomes apparent that the crash can separate itself from other percussion among this one dimension alone. To quantitatively verify this observation, we ran a binary k-Nearest Neighbours classifier in weka, with the two classes involved being “Crash” and “Not crash” and Log Attack Time as the only attribute. “Crash” is as defined in section 2.1. “Not crash” is constructed by including equal numbers of instances from each of the remaining six classes adding up to an accumulative number of sounds equal to that in the “Crash” class, thus keeping both classes balanced. Indeed, this experiment yields

a 92.26% accuracy level. The addition of Log Attack Time has now brought the classification accuracy rate to 88.49%.

Figure 25: Distribution of sounds from three cymbal types along the Spectral Entropy descriptor.

Figure 26: Distribution of all classes along the Log Attack Time dimension. Notice the Cymbal's separation level from the other 6 classes.

We move on to the “Snare versus Rim” case. Again, we can achieve a high success rate (80.91% according to scikit-learn) along just one dimension, that being the highest ranking according to the Information Gain Ratio criterion, an attribute called “Energy Band Middle Low”. This refers simply to the spectral energy included in a specific frequency band defined between a start Cut off frequency equal to 150 Hz and a stop Cut off frequency at 800 Hz [Borges, 2012].

As we can see in Figure 27, the rim sounds’ energy in that particular frequency band is generally rather low, while snares sounds’ distribution along the same dimension is much more “spread”. The two images in Figure 28 present two examples which better illustrate our observation.

Figure 27: Training set sounds belonging to the Snare and the Rim classes separated along the spectral energy of the middle-low frequency (150-800Hz) dimension.

At this point, we have reached in Weka an accuracy over 90% using only 6 features. Nevertheless this is not the case when testing the same set with the same algorithm in scikit learn. In fact, we get a lower rate, at about 85%. In an effort to further decrease our misclassification rates, we looked to run a series of six more experiments, in a manner similar to that introduced for the "crash versus not crash" case above. Our aim was to build binary classifiers using the k-Nearest Neighbour algorithm and a maximum of three features for each one of them. The choice among the available pool of descriptors was such that each model would be capable of correctly classifying sounds as belonging or not to an instrumental

class with an accuracy close to 90%, similarly to what we already achieved for the crash case using one and only attribute. This procedure resulted in us adding three more descriptors to our analysis. In the following pages, we introduce the features used in each of those classifiers, among with the success rates achieved and plots of said feature values' distribution in each case. Further explanations are given whenever any of the three additional descriptors appear. Those are limited to brief descriptions of each newly added feature. Qualitative assessment of their values for one type of sound and/or the way they compare to others was deemed too complicated and does not fall within the scope of this work.

Hi Hat: Mean of Spectral Entropy, Zero Crossing Rate and Spectral Skewness. Accuracy rate achieved: 90.86%.

We can see that a new feature is added to our analysis, the Spectral Skewness [Peeters, 2004]. The skewness is a measure of the asymmetry of a distribution around its mean value. The degree of the distribution's asymmetry is described in the following manner (see Figure 29):

- Skewness = 0 indicates a symmetric distribution
- Skewness < 0 indicates more energy on the right
- Skewness > 0 indicates more energy on the left

Figures 30 and 31 depict the Hi Hat in relation to the rest of the instruments in the space defined by the three above mentioned attributes.

Ride Cymbal: Variance of Spectral Contrast Valley of 2nd sub-band. Accuracy rate achieved: 92.19%.

This is an example that makes very little sense intuitively but was included nonetheless, given that it results in a very high accuracy rate among one single dimension. The Octave Based Spectral Contrast feature is described in [Jiang et al., 2002]. The version implemented in Essentia is a modified version to improve discriminative power and robustness, presented in [Akkermans et al., 2009]. It is a sub-band-based descriptor, given that it is calculated separately for each one of 6 distinctive octave-scaled sub-bands (with boundaries at 0, 200Hz, 400Hz, 800Hz, 1.6kHz, 3.2kHz, and 8kHz). In contrast to other similar descriptors (e.g. MFCC) which average the spectra in each sub-band and reflect the average spectral characteristics, Octave-based Spectral Contrast represents the relative spectral distribution. It does so by considering the strength of spectral peaks and spectral valleys in each sub-band separately which roughly correspond to harmonic and non-harmonic components, respectively. It is a descriptor specifically designed for genre classification and can be seen as a measure of the signal's difference to white noise. In Figure 32 we see how the Ride Cymbal separates itself from the rest due to the low variance of Spectral Valley values of its second sub-band.

Rim: Mean of Effective Duration, Zero Crossing Rate and 2nd Gammatone Cepstral Coefficient. Accuracy rate achieved = 88.53%

This algorithm computes the equivalent of MFCCs but using a Gammatone filterbank scaled on an Equivalent Rectangular Bandwidth (ERB) scale. These coefficients could be called *Gammatone Feature Cepstral Coefficients*. Gammatone filters are derived from psychophysical observations of the auditory periphery, offering a model of cochlear filtering. Their predominant use is in the speech recognition field [Shao et al., 2009].

Figures 33 and 34 depict the Rim in relation to the rest of the instruments in the space defined by the three above mentioned attributes.

Snare Drum: Mean of Zero Crossing Rate, Spectral Entropy and Energy of Mid Low (150-800 Hz) Spectral Band. Accuracy rate achieved = 91.69%

No new feature is added. Figures 35 and 36 depict the Snare Drum in relation to the rest of the instruments in the space defined by the three abovementioned attributes.

Tom: Mean of Zero Crossing Rate and Pitch Instantaneous Confidence. Accuracy rate achieved = 91.34%

No new feature is added. Figure 37 depicts the Tom in relation to the rest of the instruments in the space defined by the two above mentioned attributes.

Kick: Mean of Zero Crossing Rate and Pitch Instantaneous Confidence. Accuracy rate achieved = 90.47%

No new feature is added. Figure 38 depicts the Kick in relation to the rest of the instruments in the space defined by the two above mentioned attributes.

Aggregate list of Features

1. Mean of Pitch Instantaneous Confidence
2. Mean of Zero Crossing Rate
3. Mean of Spectral Entropy
4. Mean of Energy of Mid Low (150-800 Hz) Spectral band
5. Mean of Effective Duration
6. Mean of Spectral Skewness
7. Variance of Octave-based Spectral Contrast Valley of 2nd band
8. Log Attack Time
9. Mean of Gammatone Cepstral Coefficient number 2

Using the above 9 features for the whole, 7-class classification task, we achieve an accuracy rate of 90.17%, calculated using the scikit-learn Machine Learning python library.

Figure 28: The spectrograms of two example excerpts from the initial moments of a rim and a snare sound, along with their energy values for the mid-low frequency area.

Figure 29: Three skewness states. Image source: [Peeters, 2004]

Figure 30: Pair-wise depiction of distributions of three feature values for the case of the Hi Hat versus the 6 other instrumental classes. All axes' labels refer to mean values.

Figure 31: Three dimensional depiction of distributions of feature values for the case of the Hi Hat versus the 6 other instrumental classes. All axes' labels refer to mean values.

Figure 32: Distributions of values for the case of the Ride versus the 6 other instrumental classes, along one single dimension.

Figure 33: Pair-wise depiction of distributions of three feature values for the case of the Rim versus the 6 other instrumental classes. All axes' labels refer to mean values.

Figure 34: Three dimensional depiction of distributions of feature values for the case of the Rim versus the 6 other instrumental classes. All axes' labels refer to mean values.

Figure 35: Pair-wise depiction of distributions of three feature values for the case of the Snare Drum versus the 6 other instrumental classes. All axes' labels refer to mean values.

Figure 36: Three dimensional depiction of distributions of feature values for the case of the Snare Drum versus the 6 other instrumental classes. All axes' labels refer to mean values.

Figure 37: Pair-wise depiction of distributions of two feature values for the case of the Tom versus the 6 other instrumental classes. Both axes' labels refer to mean values.

Figure 38: Pair-wise depiction of distributions of two feature values for the case of the Kick versus the 6 other instrumental classes. Both axes' labels refer to mean values.

Chapter 4

EXPERIMENT WITH HUMAN PARTICIPANTS: MOTIVATION, DESIGN AND RESULTS

Our next concern was to use the Unconventional Sounds' set to test our classifier. Given that our task is an application of supervised learning methods, we need each one of our sounds to be labelled as belonging to one of the 7 available classes. But, by definition, this is contradictory, given that none of the sounds of the set at hand is actually part of the standard drum set. Therefore, labeling them in such a manner was achieved by simple auditory investigation, according to the perceived similarity of each sample to one of the 7 drum classes. For example, the sound of a closing oven door, being abrupt, noisy and bass-like would be attributed the Kick Drum class. Naturally, since we did not collect our samples conceiving them as reminiscent of some specific drum instrument but rather simply as having a general percussion-like quality, a big percentage among them could not be put under any category solely on the basis of our perception. Thus, the test set we used to evaluate our classifier constituted just a small percentage of the full set (to be more specific, 203 sounds, equally distributed in seven classes, resulting in 29 sounds per class).

The obtained accuracy rate (again, calculated through tenfold cross-validation) is rather low, suggesting that about 1 out of 2 input sounds are not attributed to the expected class. This should not come as a surprise: after all, we are trying to classify random non-drum sounds employing a model which has been trained with the use of sounds from the drum set. In fact, seeing as the resulting accuracy rate (49.26%) is more than three times bigger than the random chance of picking the right class, one could argue that, given the circumstances, our model has adequately perceived the attributes which characterize each instrumental sound and manages to detect hints of their presence in other percussion-like sounds. Nevertheless, it appears more likely that evaluating our system's efficiency when

used for this purpose solely by means of arithmetic criteria is inappropriate. Thus, we decided upon conducting an experiment involving human participants.

An advantage of evaluating our system with such an experiment is that, contrary to automatic procedures, it allows us to consider full drum sets instead of single instruments. That is, we can ask participants to listen to and assess drum patterns deriving from unconventional drum kits in their entirety. This is more compliant with our stated research hypothesis, given that our goal is to map non-drum sounds to instruments of a standard drum kit to be effectively used in a musical context. Judging single sonic events in isolation offers no such context.

The experiment was designed and implemented from scratch in the form of a web application, developed with the use of JavaScript and the Flask python web application framework [Fla,]. Its source code can be found in the following GitHub repository: [Stamellos, 2016]. The application includes ten drum patterns of our choice, each of which appears twice along the experiment's progress, in both cases consisting of sounds from the "unconventional" sound collection. One instance of each pattern is created with sounds that are mapped with use of our classifier to the drum instruments which would originally compose each pattern. The other is constructed with sounds that are picked at random. The selection procedure, both with the application of the classifier and the random selection was executed only once, with its results kept without any further consideration. The ensuing 20 unconventional drum sequences are the same for each and all of the participants (i.e. our experiment conforms to a *within-subject design* [Charness et al., 2012]), although presented to each of them in different, random order.

The participant is initially asked to complete a short questionnaire detailing certain relevant aspects of his/her background. More specifically, the questions are:

- Have you ever received any formal musical training?
- Do you compose music (or have you ever done so)? Either as an amateur or in a professional level, no matter the musical genre
- Do you play the drums or any other percussion instrument(s)?

The first question can be answered in three different ways (No / Yes, for less than 5 years / Yes, for more than 5 years), while the two latter give the participant a Yes or No choice.

Then, each new page of the experiment includes a sound clip which repeats a sequence in a loop, accompanied with the three following simple questions:

1. "If this pattern was performed on a conventional drum set, the result would sound similar to the above sound clip", assessing *similarity*.
2. "This sound clip could replace a conventional drum set in a musical track", assessing *substitutability*.

3. “I like this sound clip”, assessing *appreciation*.

They are all replied to with the use of a five point Likert scale, raging from “Strongly Disagree” to “Strongly Agree”. An example instance of the experiment can be seen in Figure 39. The experiment was distributed to participants through social media.

Figure 39: Screenshot of the experiment with human participants.

We gathered responses from 25 participants, whose demographic distribution in three categories according to their responses in the initial questionnaire is presented in Table 25.

The aim of the experiment is to assess whether there exists a significant difference between participants’ ratings for the sound clips produced with the use of the classifier and those for the sound clips produced using randomly chosen sounds. For the statistical analysis of our experimental data, we consider the following: we have one dependent variable (users’ ratings) which is ordinal in nature (5 point

percussion		composition		training	
not playing	17	not composing	12	not trained	9
playing	18	composing	13	trained for less than 5 years	8
total	25	total	25	trained for more than 5 years	8
				total	25

Table 25: Demographic distribution of experiment participants.

	appreciation	similarity	substitutability
all	(133.0, 0.8788)	(78.0, 0.114)	(79.5, 0.1257)
composers	(31.5, 0.5545)	(16.0, 0.1288)	(15.0, 0.0577)
drummers	(12.5, 0.7991)	(6.5, 0.2033)	(7.0, 0.2334)
non composers	(21.5, 0.3015)	(23.5, 0.3955)	(21.0, 0.5065)
non drummers	(58.0, 0.6041)	(40.0, 0.2544)	(37.0, 0.1898)
not trained	(15.5, 0.7247)	(10.5, 0.29)	(6.0, 0.3428)
trained over 5	(8.5, 0.3508)	(7.0, 0.235)	(11.0, 0.3148)
trained under 5	(15.5, 0.7247)	(10.5, 0.5527)	(3.5, 0.0411)

Table 26: Results of Wilcoxon signed ranks tests applied on the experimental data, considering all 7 demographic groups (plus the “all” case, meaning all the participants as a whole) and all 3 questions. Each tuple corresponds to: (T statistic, p value). Note that none of the comparisons (except for the one corresponding to the “trained under 5” group’s answer to the “substitutability” question) reports statistical significance of the difference between populations.

Likert scale) and one independent variable (type of sound clip) with two levels (labelled as “classifier” and “random”). The latter refer to pairs of measurements which are dependent, given that they result from users rating their impression of 10 replications of the experimental condition (all 10 drum patterns are regarded as equally important), in the form of two sound clips representing two states: the one before and the one after the application of the classifier. With the above in mind, we chose to run a *Wilcoxon signed ranks test* [Lowry, 2014], independently for each of the factors accounted for (substitutability, similarity and appreciation, corresponding to each of the three aforementioned questions) and each of the demographic categories (including all 25 participants as a whole). The result is 24 measurements (test statistic T and p value), presented in Table 26.

Significance of difference is indicated by a p value smaller than 0.05. As we see in Table 26, the only such instance is the one corresponding to the “trained under 5 years” demographic’s responses to the “substitutability” question. Thus, it is implied that participants who have had some musical training for five years at most tend to feel that the ability of the drum sets produced with the use of our classifier to substitute conventional drum sets given a musical context is significantly different

than the same ability of drum sets produced with random sounds. What is important is that no such trend is observed for participants with training which lasted for more than five years or with no training at all. Nevertheless, the Wilcoxon test cannot tell by itself which of the two types of drum sets scores higher in the substitutability factor. For a descriptive approach to the problem, we could refer to the box plots in Figure 40.

Figure 40: Box plots for three different categories of users, in reference to their answers to the 'substitutability' question.

In contrast to what we would expect, the distributions of responses from participants who have under 5 years of training appear to be very much alike for both types of drum sets. More specifically, in both cases, the second and the third quartile coincide on the “agree” response while the first one falls on the value “neutral”. This overall inconsistency can be attributed to the small sizes of samples corresponding to each of the three categories defined by the participants’ answers to the initial questionnaire’s question related to their musical training. In fact, we could hold that, out of the extracted statistics, only those calculated over the participants’ group in its entirety (i.e. those seen in the row labelled “all” of Table 26) are to be “trusted”, given that all other sub-groups considered include less than 20 subjects each. Figures 41, 42, 43 depict in the form of bar plots all answers gathered to all questions from all 25 users.

It has already been shown in Table 26 that there exists no significant difference between the “at random” and “from classifier” distributions of users’ responses

Figure 41: Bar plots for all users' responses, in reference to their answers to the 'similarity' question.

to any of the three questions. This is made more clear if we observe the above bar plots, which appear to be very similar in all three cases. The responses to the 'similarity' and 'appreciation' questions have their quartiles on the same locations (1st, 2nd and 3rd on "disagree", "neutral" and "agree", respectively) while those to the 'substitutability' question differ in regards to their 1st quartile (on "neutral" for the "at random" drum sets and on "disagree" for the "from classifier" ones).

Figure 42: Bar plots for all users' responses, in reference to their answers to the 'substitutability' question.

Figure 43: Bar plots for all users' responses, in reference to their answers to the 'appreciation' question.

Chapter 5

PROOF OF CONCEPT

As proof of concept, we developed a web application implementing a simple drum step sequencer which draws sounds from our collection of unconventional sounds in its entirety. Each time the user refreshes the web page where the application is hosted, 7 new sounds are loaded, one for each instrument corresponding to our 7 classes. The application functions by picking random sounds from our collection, inputs them to our classifier, attributes them to one of the 7 instruments and, subsequently, deletes the corresponding class from the list of our target classes. The procedure repeats until all 7 classes are deleted. Nevertheless, finding sounds which could be attributed to certain of the 7 classes (specifically, the Crash Cymbal and Snare Drum ones) after each new refresh of the web application proved to take too long. This was attributed to the fact that, out of the whole sound collection, only a small handful of sounds would be assigned to the two above mentioned classes from our 9-feature classifier. Thus, to happen upon this small set of instances while at the random selection procedure, a considerably long time interval would have to pass, making the application too difficult to use. Our solution was to slightly modify our classification system by employing three more descriptors, namely the means of the Mel Frequency Cepstral Coefficients numbers 4, 5 and 6 [Ganchev et al., 2005]. Indeed, this resulted in an increased number of sounds to be assigned to the Crash Cymbal and Snare Drum classes and, by extension, in the application to be considerably faster.

The sounds are queried from Freesound through its API, using their ids. The sequencer includes a metronome feature as well as a number of presets. Its source code can be found in the following GitHub repository: [Stamellos, 2016]. A screenshot of the sequencer is presented in Figure 44.

Figure 44: Screenshot of our proof of concept, developed in the form of a step sequencer.

Chapter 6

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Concluding this thesis, we should refer to the contributions of our work, beginning with the Drum Set Taxonomy defined in section 1.2. We believe that our Taxonomy is the most complete among the ones present in relevant literature. It is built with auditory perception in mind, treating the included instruments not simply as objects but from the viewpoint of the sounds they can produce (and, thus, include playing modes and techniques). Moreover, it adequately describes a standard drum set, given that it does not lack any of the most prevalent drum set-produced sounds neither is it “overloaded” with marginal, unusual cases.

Furthermore, we built a system which can classify drum sounds to seven target classes, corresponding to the “instrument level” of the above mentioned Taxonomy (see Figure 14). Its accuracy rate was found to be larger than 90%, calculated with tenfold cross-validation, while using less than ten features and a very simple algorithm (k-Nearest Neighbours, with $k=1$ and Manhattan distance metric). This combination of facts makes our classifier one of the most efficient ones which have been developed for the task at hand.

For the purpose of building our classification system, we had to collect a data set of drum sounds conforming to our Taxonomy. It numbers a little over 1000 sounds and is made freely available on Freesound [Fre,]. Other than that, we went ahead and built a second dataset (labelled the “unconventional dataset”), again numbering a little over 1000 instances, with random percussive-like sounds deriving from objects which were not originally designed for musical purposes. The majority of those samples was drawn from our personal recordings. The resulting dataset is also freely available in Freesound.

Our efforts resulted in a proof of concept in the form of a simple step sequencer constructing drum patterns which consist of non-drum sounds, drawn from the unconventional dataset. It functions by mapping such sounds to real drum set

instruments, employing our classification system. We hold it to be a simple yet unique tool which can be really useful in a musical creative process. Its source code is hosted in [Stamellos, 2016] and it can also be found as a web application in Freesound Labs [Fre,].

The efficiency of our system in classifying non-drum sounds was independently tested through an experiment involving human participants. The experiment did not provide any significant proof that our classifier can be effectively used for its stated purpose. This could indicate either that the chosen experimental procedure was not optimal or simply that the thesis' hypothesis cannot be verified.

The latter point directs us towards certain possible future work suggestions. More specifically, it is possible that running experiments with human participants in a different manner can lead to more relevant and more reliable results. There exists a series of such alternative options which we aim to consider and implement in the near future as to examine the classifier's efficiency more conclusively.

Moreover, the thesis' text does not include a complete justification for some of the features chosen to be used in our classifier, in the sense that they were not intuitively linked to the results they provided. For example, the variance of the Spectral Contrast Valley of frequency sub-band number 2 (200-400 Hz) was capable of separating the Ride Cymbal from the rest of the instruments on its own with a certainty of around 92%. We couldn't make much sense of this phenomenon but, given the large accuracy rate, we still did include the attribute in the analysis. The fact that this and some more attributes were inexplicably efficient for the task should form the basis for further investigation. We should research whether it does indeed make sense that they had the effect that they did and, if so, why. This could even lead to the engineering of instrument-specific features.

Finally, expanding our two data sets would definitely function to the interest of the thesis' purposes and should constitute an ongoing endeavour for future times.

Bibliography

- [Cre,] Creativecommons. <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>. [Online; accessed 05-July-2016].
- [Fla,] Flask. <http://flask.pocoo.org/>. [Online; accessed 12-August-2016].
- [Fre,] Freesound. <http://www.freesound.org/>. [Online; accessed 05-July-2016].
- [fre,] Freesound descriptors. https://www.freesound.org/docs/api/analysis_docs.html. [Online; accessed 11-July-2016].
- [Fre,] Freesoundlabs. <http://labs.freesound.org/>. [Online; accessed 27-August-2016].
- [Log,] Logit. <http://deeplearning.net/software/theano/tutorial/examples.html>. [Online; accessed 12-July-2016].
- [kNN,] scikit-learn knn. <http://scikit-learn.org/stable/modules/neighbors.html>. [Online; accessed 12-July-2016].
- [SVM,] scikit-learn svm. http://scikit-learn.org/stable/auto_examples/svm/plot_iris.html. [Online; accessed 12-July-2016].
- [sox,] Sox. <http://sox.sourceforge.net/>. [Online; accessed 05-July-2016].
- [Dur,] standard duration. http://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/reference/std_Duration.html. [Online; accessed 11-August-2016].
- [str,] streaming derivativesfx. http://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/reference/streaming_DerivativeSFX.html. [Online; accessed 11-August-2016].

- [ext, a] streaming extractor freesound. http://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/extractors_out_of_box.html. [Online; accessed 11-July-2016].
- [ext, b] streaming extractor music. http://essentia.upf.edu/documentation/streaming_extractor_music.html. [Online; accessed 11-July-2016].
- [Zoo,] Zoom h1. <https://www.zoom-na.com/products/field-video-recording/field-recording/zoom-h1-handly-recorder>. [Online; accessed 29-August-2016].
- [Akkermans et al., 2009] Akkermans, V., Serrà, J., and Herrera, P. (2009). Shape-based spectral contrast descriptor. In *Proc. of the Sound and Music Computing Conf.(SMC)*, pages 143–148.
- [Batista and Souza-filho, 2015] Batista, G. E. A. P. A. and Souza-filho, N. E. (2015). Automatic Classification of Drum Sounds with Indefinite Pitch. pages 1–8.
- [Bilbao, 2012] Bilbao, S. (2012). Time domain simulation and sound synthesis for the snare drum. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 131(1):914–25.
- [Borges, 2012] Borges, R. C. (2012). Noise/signal: two different listening experiences for deterministic and non deterministic sound stimulus. In *Acoustics 2012*.
- [Chaigne et al., 2004] Chaigne, A., Touzé, C., and Thomas, O. (2004). Mechanical models of musical instruments and sound synthesis: the case of gongs and cymbals. In *Proc. Int. Symp. on Musical Acoustics (Nara, Japan)*.
- [Charness et al., 2012] Charness, G., Gneezy, U., and Kuhn, M. A. (2012). Experimental methods: Between-subject and within-subject design. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 81(1):1–8.
- [De Cheveigné and Kawahara, 2002] De Cheveigné, A. and Kawahara, H. (2002). Yin, a fundamental frequency estimator for speech and music. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 111(4):1917–1930.
- [Domingos, 2012] Domingos, P. (2012). A few useful things to know about machine learning. *Communications of the ACM*, 55(10):78–87.

- [FitzGerald and Paulus, 2006] FitzGerald, D. and Paulus, J. (2006). Unpitched percussion transcription. In *Signal Processing Methods for Music Transcription*, pages 131–162. Springer.
- [Freed, 1990] Freed, D. J. (1990). Auditory correlates of perceived mallet hardness for a set of recorded percussive sound events. *The Journal of the Acoustical Society of America*, 87(1):311–322.
- [Friedman, 1997] Friedman, J. H. (1997). On bias, variance, 0/1-loss and the curse-of-dimensionality. *Data mining and knowledge discovery*, 1(1):55–77.
- [Galar et al., 2012] Galar, M., Fern, A., Barrenechea, E., and Bustince, H. (2012). Hybrid-Based Approaches. 42(4):463–484.
- [Ganchev et al., 2005] Ganchev, T., Fakotakis, N., and Kokkinakis, G. (2005). Comparative evaluation of various mfcc implementations on the speaker verification task. In *Proceedings of the SPECOM*, volume 1, pages 191–194.
- [Gouyon and Herrera, 2001] Gouyon, F. and Herrera, P. (2001). Exploration of techniques for automatic labeling of audio drum tracks instruments. ... *on Current Directions in Computer Music*.
- [Gouyon et al., 2000] Gouyon, F., Pachet, F., and Delerue, O. (2000). On the use of Zero-Crossing rate for an application of classification of percussive sounds. *Dafx*, pages 3–8.
- [Guyon and Elisseeff, 2003] Guyon, I. and Elisseeff, A. (2003). An introduction to variable and feature selection. *Journal of machine learning research*, 3(Mar):1157–1182.
- [Hawkins, 2004] Hawkins, D. M. (2004). The problem of overfitting. *Journal of chemical information and computer sciences*, 44(1):1–12.
- [Hazan, 2005] Hazan, A. (2005). Towards automatic transcription of expressive oral percussive performances. In *Proceedings of the 10th international conference on Intelligent user interfaces*, pages 296–298. ACM.
- [He and Garcia, 2009] He, H. and Garcia, E. A. (2009). Learning from imbalanced data. *IEEE Transactions on Knowledge and Data Engineering*, 21(9):1263–1284.
- [Herrera et al., 2003] Herrera, P., Dehamel, A., and Gouyon, F. (2003). Automatic Labelling of Unpitched Percussion Sounds. *Aes 114Th Convention*.

- [Herrera et al., 2002] Herrera, P., Yeterian, A., and Gouyon, F. (2002). Automatic classification of drum sounds : a comparison of feature selection methods and classification techniques. *Music and Artificial Intelligence*, pages 69–80.
- [Herrero et al., 2015] Herrero, G., Barbancho, I., Tardón, L. J., Rosa-Pujazón, A., and Barbancho, A. M. (2015). Drumkit simulator from everyday desktop objects. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 74(23):10195–10213.
- [Howard, David M., Angus, 2009] Howard, David M., Angus, J. (2009). *ACOUSTICS AND PSYCHOACOUSTICS*, volume 1.
- [Jiang et al., 2002] Jiang, D.-N., Lu, L., Zhang, H.-J., Tao, J.-H., and Cai, L.-H. (2002). Music type classification by spectral contrast feature. In *Multimedia and Expo, 2002. ICME'02. Proceedings. 2002 IEEE International Conference on*, volume 1, pages 113–116. IEEE.
- [Kapur et al., 2004] Kapur, A., Benning, M., and Tzanetakis, G. (2004). Query-by-beat-boxing: Music retrieval for the DJ. *Proceedings of the International*
- [Klatzky et al., 2000] Klatzky, R. L., Pai, D. K., and Krotkov, E. P. (2000). Perception of material from contact sounds. *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 9(4):399–410.
- [Lakatos, 2000] Lakatos, S. (2000). A common perceptual space for harmonic and percussive timbres. *Perception & psychophysics*, 62(7):1426–1439.
- [Lewis and Beckford, 2000] Lewis, R. and Beckford, J. (2000). Measuring tonal characteristics of snare drum batter heads. *Percussive Notes*, 38(3):69–71.
- [Lowry, 2014] Lowry, R. (2014). Concepts and applications of inferential statistics.
- [Misra et al., 2004] Misra, H., Ikbal, S., Bourlard, H., and Hermansky, H. (2004). Spectral entropy based feature for robust asr. In *Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing, 2004. Proceedings.(ICASSP'04). IEEE International Conference on*, volume 1, pages I–193. IEEE.
- [Norris Jr, 2003] Norris Jr, T. M. (2003). Drum pillow and method for using same. US Patent 6,573,441.
- [Olivier Gillet, 2004] Olivier Gillet, G. R. (2004). Automatic Transcription of Drum Loops. *Evaluation*, pages 2–5.

- [Peeters, 2004] Peeters, G. (2004). A large set of audio features for sound description (similarity and classification) in the CUIDADO project. Technical report, IRCAM, Paris, France.
- [Quackenbush and Lindsay, 2001] Quackenbush, S. and Lindsay, A. (2001). Overview of MPEG-7 audio. *IEEE Transactions on Circuits and Systems for Video Technology*, 11(6):725–729.
- [Rossing, 2001] Rossing, T. D. (2001). Acoustics of percussion instruments: Recent progress. *Acoustical Science and Technology*, 22(3):177–188.
- [Shahar, 2010] Shahar, E. (2010). Automatic drum samples classification, a final project for pattern recognition. http://alumni.media.mit.edu/~persones/pattern_rec/patternrec.html. [Online; accessed 03-July-2016].
- [Shao et al., 2009] Shao, Y., Jin, Z., Wang, D., and Srinivasan, S. (2009). An auditory-based feature for robust speech recognition. In *2009 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing*, pages 4625–4628. IEEE.
- [Sillanpää et al., 2000] Sillanpää, J., Klapuri, A., Seppänen, J., and Virtanen, T. (2000). Recognition of acoustic noise mixtures by combined bottom-up and top-down processing. In *Proceedings of the European Signal Processing Conference EUSIPCO*, volume 1, pages 335–338. Citeseer.
- [Smith, 1986] Smith, P. L. (1986). Foot operated bass drum pedal. US Patent 4,567,808.
- [Stamellos, 2016] Stamellos, L. (2016). smc thesis. https://github.com/LefterisStamellos/smc_thesis.
- [Stowell and Plumbley, 2010] Stowell, D. and Plumbley, M. D. (2010). Delayed decision-making in real-time beatbox percussion classification. *Journal of New Music Research*, 39(3):203–213.
- [Tindale et al., 2004] Tindale, A., Kapur, A., Tzanetakis, G., and Fujinaga, I. (2004). Retrieval of percussion gestures using timbre classification techniques. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Music Information Retrieval*, pages 541–545.
- [Van Steelant et al., 2005] Van Steelant, D., Tanghe, K., Degroeve, S., De Baets, B., Leman, M., and Martens, J. P. (2005). Support Vector Machines for bass and snare drum recognition. *Studies in Classification, Data Analysis, and Knowledge Organization*, pages 616–623.

- [Von Hornbostel and Sachs, 1961] Von Hornbostel, E. M. and Sachs, C. (1961). Classification of musical instruments: Translated from the original german by anthony baines and klaus p. wachsmann. *The Galpin Society Journal*, pages 3–29.
- [Wheeler, 1989] Wheeler, D. (1989). Focus on research: Some experiments concerning the effect of snares on the snare drum sound. *Percussive Notes*, 27(4):48–52.
- [Wiggins, 2009] Wiggins, G. A. (2009). Semantic gap?? Schemantic schmap!! Methodological considerations in the scientific study of music. *ISM 2009 - 11th IEEE International Symposium on Multimedia*, pages 477–482.